

D1.2 eMetrics for explainability and trustworthy

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Author(s)/ Organisation(s)	UNS, BUL, TID, CNR		
Contributor(s)	Ben Malin, Tatiana Kalganova, Nikolaos Boulgouris (BUL) Suzic Sinisa, Vuk Stanojev (UNS) Jordi Luque Serrano, David Solans, Aleix Sant Savall (TID) Giuseppe Caggianese, Filippo Vella (CNR) Sergio Burdisso, Dairazalia Sanchez-Cortes, Petr Motlicek (IDIAP) Nikos Arvanitis (SYN) Alessio Brutti (FBK)		
Abstract	<p>Deliverable 1.2 focuses on the evaluation methodologies that can be harnessed for the ongoing assessment and improvement of the ELOQUENCE Project. Extensive literature review has been performed across the domains of faithfulness, explainability, and bias. With experimental work having been performed, outputting various metrics, for the faithfulness and explainability domains – leading to the production of fused ELOQUENCE metrics (eMetrics), which are made publicly available online. Across this deliverable, Pilots 1,2 and 4 have been experimentally evaluated for both faithfulness and explainability, allowing for subsequent evaluation and analysis as techniques are further honed. LLM-as-a-judge techniques currently lead the way for individual metrics that have been correlated against human judgements (which have been gathered and made available as part of the ELOQUENCE fused dataset) for faithfulness. However, additional metrics (such as n-grams and BERTScore) are fused together to form a faithfulness eMetric, which demonstrates superior correlation with human judgement. Whilst graph-based outputs have been extensively trialled for enhancing the level of explainability that can be provided to a user. Finally, extensive research has been conducted in the realms of bias evaluation and privacy evaluation, so that these domains can be efficiently implemented within the eMetrics in the future as part of milestone 1.3.</p>		

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Participant No.	Participant organisation name	Short name	Country	Role*
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2	CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE	CNR	IT	BEN
3	BARCELONA SUPERCOMPUTING CENTER CENTRO NACIONAL DE SUPERCOMPUTACION	BSC	ES	BEN
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ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

ASR	Automatic Speech Recognition
AMR	Abstract Meaning Representation
COT	Chain-of-Thought
DP-SGD	Differentially Private Stochastic Gradient Descent
FAISS	Facebook AI Similarity Search
FT	Fine Tuning
KR	Key result
LLM	Large Language Model
MT	Machine Translation
NER	Named Entity Recognition
NQ	Natural Questions
QA	Question-Answering
PII	Person Identifiable Information
PTC	Predict-then-Compute
RAG	Retrieval Augmented Generation
ROUGE	Recall-Oriented Understudy for Gisting Evaluation
STAR	Schema-guided Dialog Dataset for Transfer Learning
TOD	Task-Oriented-Dialogue
IR	Information Retrieval
WSD	Word Sense Disambiguation
WP	Work Package
WuW	Wake-up-Word

1 Executive Summary

This report details the second deliverable produced as part of WP1, outlining the efforts made to achieve ELOQUENCE's goal of introducing novel eMetrics that incorporate both explainability and trustworthiness evaluation, so that the user can have faith in the model's output. The broader objectives of WP1 involve the research and evaluation of semi-structured, multi-turn and unstructured dialogues. This deliverable is closely linked with deliverable 1.1, as many of the metrics that have been chosen for evaluation in the trustworthiness domain have been done so resultant from extensive literature review conducted as part of deliverable 1.1.

Milestone 1.2 is tied to this deliverable, requiring the produced eMetrics to be made available to the partners, alongside evaluation results that have been performed on the open-source fused dataset (that has been developed as part of Milestone 1.1, and further honed throughout the work conducted on Milestone 1.2). The fused dataset, and code repository for reproduction of the eMetrics, is available at <https://huggingface.co/datasets/Brunel-AI/ELOQUENCE/>.

This deliverable begins with evaluation on this fused dataset, for the purpose of evaluating faithfulness (which is heavily aligned with trustworthiness), along with faithfulness evaluations that have been performed on pilot data. These automated metrics are then correlated against human judgements regarding faithfulness, to identify the metrics that are most highly correlated with human judgements – for their validation. Following the faithfulness experimentation, work detailing explainability and the use of various strategies to incorporate explainability metrics as well as outputs to aid the user's understanding of LLM outputs. Literature review for the evaluation of the security and privacy for the federate learning aspects of the project is produced, though the experimental work for this section is more relevant to future objectives. Various categories of bias are then reviewed, with literature review provided, in the aims of evaluating the level of bias that is produced by the LLMs implemented. These bias-related metrics can then be incorporated in later versions of the fused eMetrics that are being developed. Finally, the production of fused metrics is discussed, utilizing the implementation of both faithfulness and explainability metrics into a single metric, to aid in the dissemination and streamlining of evaluation. As WP1 tasks are further worked on, additional metrics are to be incorporated, such as multilinguality and multi-modality metrics.

2 Introduction

Although the evaluation of dialogue systems is a crucial step in their development, this process remains challenging for two main reasons (Deriu and al. 2021) the strong dependence on the system’s application context and the resource limitations arising from the need for human involvement. As further discussed in (Deriu and al. 2021), several key requirements should be met: the evaluation procedure should be automatic, repeatable, correlated with human judgments, explainable, and adaptable to different systems.

This report presents the activities carried out within the ELOQUENCE project related to system evaluation. Since dialogue systems can be assessed across multiple dimensions—such as accuracy, ethics, fairness, and explainability (Hu y Zhou 2024)—we examined metrics covering different domains such as faithfulness, explainability, privacy, cultural bias, and gender bias. The work described in this report was primarily conducted on open datasets, though it also includes results from specific metrics evaluated on ELOQUENCE pilot data. Furthermore, we introduce the fused ELOQUENCE metric, which combines multiple individual metrics into a single aggregated score that correlates with human judgments.

The remainder of this document is organized as follows:

- Chapter 3 presents our investigation in the domain of faithfulness. It evaluates the performance of several established faithfulness metrics on the fused dataset and examines the behavior of multiple automatic metrics on the pilot-specific data, including their correlation with human judgments.
- Chapter 4 focuses on our work in the field of explainability. Using an open dataset, this section reports on the evaluation of graph-based metrics for assessing question answering and dialogue summarization tasks. It also introduces the explainability evaluation in the context of pilot-specific scenarios.
- Chapter 5 discusses the evaluation of security, with focus on the risks and ways in which risks can be mitigated, as well as metrics that can be implemented for federated learning.
- Chapter 6 summarizes the results of the evaluation of different types of bias relevant to the project-specific pilots. The following categories were investigated: multilingual bias, cultural bias, gender bias, and multimodal bias.
- Chapter 7 introduces the ELOQUENCE-specific eMetric, which integrates several previously presented metrics into a single composite score. In addition, it identifies those metrics that show the strongest correlation with human judgments.
- Chapter 8 summarizes the key findings presented in the whole document.

3 Faithfulness evaluation

3.1 Introduction

Faithfulness within the realm of Large Language Models (LLMs) refers to their ability to produce trustworthy and reliable outputs. This has major implications in the domains that they can be applied within, as it has been noted that LLMs are prone to "hallucinate" outputs and provide nonfactual information to the user. These "hallucinations" diminish the applicability of LLMs in many contexts, most notably when related to safety-critical applications whereby erroneous information can incur major consequences. Evaluating the faithfulness of LLM outputs is a growing field due to this desirability for LLM reliability and user-confidence. There are a wide-range of metrics that have been commonly utilised in the assessment of faithfulness, with some being more prevalent within specific domains (such as summarisation or question-answering).

The ability to reliably evaluate faithfulness can allow for greater confidence to be placed in LLMs, whilst also allowing for alternative approaches to be taken in directly improving faithfulness. Most notably this can refer to reprompting strategies (Li 2025), whereby the LLM is tasked with regenerating the output given additional context, with the aim of mitigating the risk of hallucination.

3.2 Fused dataset evaluation

This chapter focuses on evaluating LLM faithfulness using the ELOQUENCE fused dataset across a range of commonplace metrics, as well as applying faithfulness-improving approaches that have been demonstrated by other authors, in novel domains. This is done to build confidence in LLM outputs, enabling their implementation in a wider range of scenarios where accountability is key and potentially unethical outcomes must be avoided.

3.2.1 Human Evaluation

Within the NQ (Kwiatkowski 2019) subset, long-form and short-form LLM responses have been evaluated against their respective ground-truth answers, with human judgments provided which consider the context of the question and the alignment between response and answer. When there is uncertainty over the faithfulness of a response, the human assessors can abstain from providing a judgment and these samples are not considered for the correlation. It is important to note that the ground-truths may not always be factual (commonly due to outdated information within the dataset) but should be treated as such and thus external knowledge is not used to deem a response to be faithful if it is not aligned with the ground-truth.

Human judgements have been collected using a Python script which displays the question, any additional context (such as a dialogue transcript), the ground truth answers/summaries as well as the LLM-generated answers/summaries. For all domains a score of 1-5 is annotated for the LLM response, this is then additionally represented as a human boolean value, whereby scores of 3-5 are considered a 1 (faithful) and scores below 3 are scored as a 0 (unfaithful). For the summarisation domain, humans perform this judgement for each LLM summarised point, with the mean then taken and used to represent the overall faithfulness of the LLM's response. This process is utilised due to the additional ambiguity found within the summarisation domain, as well as to allow for evaluation of individual facts within a larger summary - which has demonstrated superior correlation with human judgement in several studies (Kim 2024, Min 2023).

3.2.2 Methodology

The Llama 3.1-8B ¹ instruct model has been used to generate responses for the various tasks within the dataset, utilising a greedy search strategy (ensuring that outputs are deterministic) and setting the maximum new tokens to 256. All tasks use an in-context learning approach, whereby example outputs are incorporated into the prompt, improving the consistency of the generated outputs.

The prompts used differ across the tasks, and all prompts are included within the appendix.

¹ <https://huggingface.co/meta-llama/Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct>

To increase the granularity of the LLM's faithfulness evaluation, two approaches have been trialled. The first utilises logits to determine the confidence of the faithfulness prediction and subsequently alter the score from a Boolean measurement to a continuous measurement between 0 and 1. The second approach prompts the LLM to output the degree of faithfulness on a 5-point Likert scale. These are referred to as the LLM Confidence approach and the LLM Likert approach respectively. Both techniques have been assessed before, and been shown to improve faithfulness evaluation capabilities. Furthermore, the speakers have been identified across the dialogue and formatted as a separate attribute.

3.2.2.1 Question-Answering

Natural Questions (NQ) (Kwiatkowski 2019) has been selected due to the presence of long-form and short-form answers, providing greater scope for the assessment of the suitability of fact extraction techniques. In addition, the PopQA dataset (Mallen 2023) is incorporated into the fused dataset due to the presence of fact tuples. However, only entity-based answers are present, limiting the evaluation of long-form faithfulness for this dataset. Similarly, the QAConv (Wu 2022) dataset has been incorporated within the fused dataset for extractive QA evaluation and features multi-turn dialogue between several speakers with QA pairs relating to the dialogue.

3.2.2.2 Dialogue Summarisation

The dialogue summarisation domain involves long-form text, often in the form of multi-turn dialogue between multiple speakers, with the key points summarised in a concise manner. These summaries are typically human produced and can feature the key points separated (which can be referred to as atomic facts or more typically as a paragraph). The SAMSum (Gliwa 2019) dataset has been selected for fusion into the dialogue summarisation domain of this fused dataset due to the presence of human annotated summaries and multi-turn dialogue.

3.2.2.3 Extractive QA

The final domain for which faithfulness evaluation is experimentally evaluated is conversational QA, which contains dialogue between multiple speakers, with QA pairs relating to the dialogue. This is desirable for evaluation, as LLMs cannot use inherent knowledge to answer questions, and thus it is more closely aligned with reading comprehension tasks. Additionally, the relevant text that is required for processing is significantly larger than in non-conversational QA domains, further validating the selected metrics across different use cases. To evaluate this domain, the QA Conv. dataset (Wu 2022) has been selected and utilised within the fused dataset. It contains multi-turn dialogues that are separated by speaker, as well as a question per dialogue, with one or more correct answers per question. Human judgements have been collected and appended within the fused dataset's conversational QA subset for evaluation.

3.2.3 Metrics

Extensive faithfulness evaluation review has been conducted, covering metrics that have been utilized for faithfulness across a range of relevant domains for the ELOQUENCE project (Malin 2025).

3.2.3.1 LLM-as-a-judge for ELOQUENCE fused dataset (BUL)

The level of adaptability across domains offered by LLM-as-a-judge techniques, using the Llama-3.1 8B instruct model, makes them incredibly versatile. Additionally, they commonly attain the strongest correlation with human judgements, proving that more trust can be placed within these metrics compared to some of the more traditional metrics, even domain-specific metrics. Increasing the level of granularity of LLM faithfulness outputs improved the correlation with human judgement, with two methodologies tested: prompting the LLMs to output Likert scores of 1-5 and requesting binary faithfulness scores which are then converted to continuous values through token logits. The latter of these two techniques was frequently the best-performing metric across domains.

We also find that for QA tasks, most metrics are more faithful evaluators when answers are concise, with very strong correlations observed for LLM-as-a-judge techniques for short-form QA.

The code to produce these faithfulness eMetrics, along with the fused dataset, is provided at <https://huggingface.co/datasets/Brunel-AI/ELOQUENCE/>

3.3 Pilot Evaluations

3.3.1 Pilot 1 Evaluation – TID

To evaluate the assistant developed in Pilot 1, we use an in-house recorded test set composed of simulated smart home interactions in Spanish, performed at a domestic environment at the UX Lab in Telefónica Innovación Digital. This dataset includes audio recordings, human-validated transcriptions, annotated speaker turns and semantic layers designed for comprehension tasks. It features both extractive and abstractive question–answer pairs, along with concise summaries to support dialogue understanding and summarization.

3.3.1.1 Test Set

Currently, the test set is comprised of five dialogues have been recorded, curated and annotated, each involving three to four speakers and totalling 42.23 minutes of conversation (Conversation 1: 6.25 min, conversation 2: 4.23 min, conversation 3: 11.16 min, conversation 4: 8.02 min and conversation 5: 12.09 min)

Each sample in this new dialogue-based dataset follows the structured format shown below:

```
{
  "dialogue_00": {
    "turns": { ... },
    "questions": {
      "extractive": { ... },
      "abstractive": { ... }
    },
    "summary": "...
  }
}
```

The *turns* field is a dictionary that contains every utterance (or dialogue turn) of the conversation. Each entry in the dictionary is a turn, uniquely identified by its ID, and includes the transcribed text in the *text* field along with its speaker label in the *speaker* field. The transcription was first obtained using WhisperX technology and later curated and improved by a human.

```
"turns": {
  "0": {
    "text": "Cariño, ya estoy en casa con los chavales.",
    "speaker": "Javier"
  },
  "1": {
    "text": "Hola, ¿qué tal? ¿Qué tal ha ido el partido?",
    "speaker": "Linda"
  }
  // ...
}
```

The *questions* field is a dictionary that organizes comprehensive natural language questions about the dialogue into two categories based on the type of reasoning required to answer the question: **extractive** and **abstractive**.

- **Extractive** questions are those whose answers appear explicitly in the dialogue. While understanding the context across multiple turns may be necessary, the answer is typically stated directly in one or more utterances. These questions include detailed span annotations to precisely locate the answer within the transcript.
- **Abstractive** questions require a higher level of reasoning or synthesis. Their answers are not explicitly stated in the dialogue; instead, they demand dialog understanding, integration of multiple turns and interpretation of implicit context. Responding to these questions often involves deducing meanings, emotions or intentions that go beyond what is literally expressed. In other words, they require understanding the underlying relationships, motivations and nuances rather than simply extracting surface-level information.

To generate and annotate these questions and answers, we combined the use of powerful LLMs to propose candidate items with manual reading and annotation. In all cases, every question and answer was thoroughly reviewed and manually-validated to ensure accuracy and high-quality annotation.

Each question is stored as a dictionary, accessed by its unique *question* ID. The structure of each question dictionary includes the following information:

```
{
  "extractive": {
    "0": {
      "question": "What school subjects does the mother have a good memory of?",
      "answer_info": {
        "answer": [["English"],["maths","mathematics"]],
        "turn_ids": ["113", "114", "115", "116", "117", "119"],
        "span": {
          "115": [{ "span_start": 152, "span_end": 156 }],
          "116": [{ "span_start": 19, "span_end": 23 }],
          "117": [{ "span_start": 23, "span_end": 27 }],
          "119": [{ "span_start": 29, "span_end": 34 },
                 { "span_start": 145, "span_end": 150 }]
        }
      }
    },
    "is_impossible": false
  },
  "1": {
    // ...
  }
}
}
```

Each dictionary in the **extractive** section contains a *question* field with the natural language question (i.e., query) and an *is_impossible* field, a boolean indicating whether the dialogue provides an answer (true means the question cannot be answered). When an answer is explicitly present in the transcript, the entry additionally includes an *answer_info* field with three components:

- *Answer*: a list of lists containing the required answer strings, including acceptable lexical variants (e.g., “maths” / “mathematics”).
- *Turn_ids*: a list of the dialogue turn IDs that provide the answer or relevant supporting context.
- *Span*: a mapping from each referenced turn ID to one or more-character spans (*span_start*, *span_end*) that precisely locate the answer within the transcription.

If an answer is not explicitly stated in the dialogue, the dictionary contains only the *question* field and *is_impossible* is set to True.

For the **abstractive** questions, each question is again represented as a dictionary identified by the question ID and contains the following information:

```
{
  "abstractive": {
    "0": {
      "question": "Why does Javier tell Alex not to call him \"sir\"? ",
      "answer": "Because he wants to be treated with trust and closeness, not formality."
    },
    "1": {
      // ...
    }
  }
}
```

}

Each dictionary within the **abstractive** questions represents a single question and contains two fields. The *question* field stores the natural language question formulated about the dialogue. The *answer* field provides a concise response that may combine information from multiple dialogue turns, require inference or reasoning, rather than being directly quoted from the text. Unlike the extractive case, abstractive questions do not include *answer_info* or *is_impossible* fields, since the answers are not directly tied to explicit text spans.

In our evaluation setup, **extractive questions** will be used to assess the model's ability to perform precise information retrieval and text grounding, whereas **abstractive questions** will evaluate its capacity to infer, reason and generate coherent responses based on implicit or distributed contextual cues.

Finally, the *summary* field provides a short narrative synopsis of the entire dialogue, capturing the main events, participants and outcomes in a coherent and human-readable form.

To further enhance the dataset, we plan to include precise timestamps of the audio recordings for the answer spans of extractive questions, creating a resource similar to the Conversational Podcast-driven Multi-modal FIR Dataset ([D2.2, Section 3](#)). This addition will enable FIR task from both text (transcripts) and audio (speech), providing not only character-level spans in the transcript but also corresponding audio snippets for each answer. By grounding the dataset in spontaneous, disfluent and context-rich human dialogue, we ensure that the retrieval task reflects the complexity and authenticity of real conversational speech.

3.3.1.1 LLM Prompts for Response Generation

This section describes the prompts used (Spanish) for each task performed by the LLM. Each task includes the base prompt and a brief explanation of how examples were constructed.

1. Extractive QA

Prompt:

```
Contesta la siguiente pregunta basándote únicamente en el diálogo dado.
No inventes información que no aparezca en el texto. Si no se puede
saber la respuesta devuelve exactamente: Incontestable.
Responde de forma breve y directa, sin explicaciones, sin frases
adicionales, sin repetir la pregunta.
```

```
Diálogo:
{{dialogue}}
```

```
{{examples}}
Pregunta: {{question}}
Respuesta:
```

Example Construction:

Each conversation required its own examples, as the questions depend on the specific dialogue. We always include one answerable and one unanswerable example to guide the model. An example for the first conversation can be seen below:

```
Pregunta: ¿Cómo se llama el amigo de Tommy?
Respuesta: Alex.
Pregunta: ¿Cómo se llama la abuela de Tommy?
Respuesta: Incontestable.
```

2. Abstractive QA

Prompt:

Responde la siguiente pregunta basándote únicamente en el diálogo proporcionado.

Genera una respuesta abstractiva que refleje una comprensión profunda del intercambio, incluyendo emociones, intenciones y relaciones entre los hablantes.

No repitas literalmente el diálogo: sintetiza y reformula.

Devuelve solo UNA frase, clara y coherente.

Diálogo:

{{dialogue}}

{{examples}}

Pregunta: {{question}}

Respuesta:

Example Construction:

As with Extractive QA, examples were created per conversation. Below is a one-shot example used for the second dialogue:

Pregunta: ¿Qué sugiere la reacción de Sara al ver las fotos de Emma y Tommy?

Respuesta: Que siente cariño por ellos y le sorprende cuánto han crecido, lo que indica que los conoce desde hace tiempo.

3. Summarization

Prompt:

Eres un asistente experto en análisis conversacional. Tu tarea es leer el siguiente diálogo y generar un resumen narrativo detallado, similar a una sinopsis, que incluya:

- Quiénes participan y cuál es su relación.
- El contexto general (por qué se encuentran, dónde están, tono de la conversación).
- Los temas principales tratados (actividades, planes, emociones, detalles relevantes).
- Información implícita (intenciones, vínculos, intereses).
- Evita repetir frases textuales del diálogo; sintetiza e interpreta de forma natural y coherente.
- Usa un estilo descriptivo, informal y fluido, como si contaras la escena a alguien más.

Diálogo:

{dialogue}

Genera un resumen narrativo completo del diálogo anterior, siguiendo las indicaciones.

Resumen:

For this task, the model was prompted in zero-shot, as no examples were required.

3.3.1.2 Metrics

For the extractive QA task, we are planning to compute three metrics: **Exact Match**, **Answer Coverage Score**, **BERTScore (F1)**, **LLM-as-a-judge** (extractive case) and **Answerability Accuracy**.

- 1) The **Exact Match** score evaluates whether the model’s prediction exactly matches any valid gold-standard answer formulation. Since some answers contain multiple required components with several acceptable variants, we generate all possible full-answer combinations by selecting one variant per component and constructing the corresponding string (e.g., “A, B y C”). The Exact Match score is 1 if the model’s normalized prediction matches any of these combinations, and 0 otherwise. This metric enforces strict correctness and only accepts predictions that reproduce one of the valid formulations verbatim, without allowing paraphrasing or partial matches.

- 2) The **Answer Coverage Score** measures how much of the gold-standard answer is captured in the model’s prediction, accounting for multiple required components or acceptable variants. To compute this score, both the model’s prediction and all ground-truth answer variants are first normalized through lowercasing and punctuation removal. Each ground-truth “item”, such as names, times or locations, contributes equally to the total score, and an item is considered correctly predicted if any of its acceptable variants appears fully in the model’s answer. The final score is calculated as the fraction of items correctly recovered, ranging from 0 to 1.
This metric provides a fine-grained assessment, capturing partial correctness when answers include multiple essential elements. While it improves upon traditional Exact Match by allowing more nuanced scoring, its main limitation is that it does not penalize incorrect elements introduced by the model, focusing solely on the presence of expected components in the prediction.

- 3) The **BERTScore (F1)** for the extractive setting measures the semantic similarity between the model’s answer and all valid gold-standard variants. Because extractive answers may contain multiple required components with several acceptable formulations, we generate every possible full-answer combination (e.g., “A, B y C”) and compute precision, recall, and F1 at the token level between each combination and the model’s prediction using XLM-RoBERTa-large, a multilingual embedding model suitable for Spanish. The final score is the maximum F1 obtained across all combinations, ensuring that the model receives credit if its answer semantically aligns with any valid variant. This approach captures meaning preservation even when the model introduces minor reformulations, while still respecting the structured nature of multi-component extractive answers.

- 4) For the **LLM-as-a-judge (Extractive)**, we complement the rule-based metrics with an additional layer of evaluation using a second LLM acting as an impartial judge. Specifically, we use the gemma-3-27b-it² model from Google in a 4-bit quantized format. To assess the model’s prediction, the judge receives the full dialogue, the question, the structured ground truth (including all acceptable variants and required components) and the model’s predicted answer. Based on this information, it must classify the prediction strictly as “CORRECTA”, “PARCIAL” or “INCORRECTA”, following predefined rules that account for answer coverage, missing elements and potential hallucinations. These qualitative labels are then mapped to numerical values of 1, 2, and 3, respectively, to get a final numeric score. This metric provides a more human-aligned assessment of correctness. It is particularly valuable in cases where the model’s answer is phrased differently from the ground truth, uses synonyms or paraphrases, or includes slight variations that our previous rule-based methods may not adequately capture.

The prompt used for the judge is:

```
Eres un juez de respuestas extractivas.
```

```
Recibirás:
```

1. Una transcripción de un diálogo.
2. Una pregunta sobre el diálogo.
3. Un Ground Truth que es una lista de GRUPOS con variantes aceptables.

² https://huggingface.co/google/gemma-3-27b-it-gat-q4_0-gguf

4. Una respuesta propuesta por el usuario.

Tu tarea: Clasificar la respuesta del usuario como CORRECTA, PARCIAL o INCORRECTA según el Ground Truth.

Definición del Ground Truth:

- Cada GRUPO contiene variantes aceptables (sinónimos, reformulaciones...).
- La respuesta es CORRECTA si menciona al menos UNA variante de CADA grupo.
- Es PARCIAL si menciona variantes de algunos grupos, pero no de todos.
- Es INCORRECTA si no menciona variantes de ningún grupo.
- Si la respuesta menciona al menos UNA variante de CADA grupo pero añade elementos que no aparecen en el Ground Truth, la respuesta es PARCIAL.

Ejemplo:

Ground Truth: [['10:30', 'diez y media'], ['María', 'María del Mar']]

- 10:30 y María del Mar -> Respuesta: CORRECTA.
- 10:30, María del Mar y otoño -> Respuesta: PARCIAL.
- 10:30 -> Respuesta: PARCIAL.
- 8:30 y María -> Respuesta: PARCIAL.
- Juan y Pablo -> Respuesta: INCORRECTA.
- Incontestable -> Respuesta: INCORRECTA.
- Nada -> Respuesta: INCORRECTA.

Reglas estrictas:

- Evalúa ÚNICAMENTE si la respuesta del usuario incluye las unidades requeridas según el Ground Truth. Céntrate en el Ground Truth.
- Devuelve como salida solo una palabra: CORRECTA, PARCIAL o INCORRECTA.
- NO añadas explicaciones ni texto adicional.

Diálogo:

```
{{dialogue}}
```

```
{{example}}
```

```
Pregunta: {{question}}
```

```
Ground Truth: {{gt_answer}}
```

```
Respuesta del usuario: {{candidate_answer}}
```

```
Respuesta:
```

- 5) For the **Answerability Accuracy**, we evaluate whether the model correctly distinguishes between extractive questions that should be answered and those that have no answer in the dialogue and must therefore be labelled as *Incontestable* (as specified in the prompt during model querying). The procedure is as follows: the model's prediction is normalized; it is compared either to the canonical "incontestable" response when the question is unanswerable; and finally, accuracy is then computed across all questions. This metric reflects the model's ability to avoid hallucination and recognize when information is absent from the context.

For the abstractive QA task, we are going to compute these other metrics: **ROUGE-L**, **BERTScore** and **LLM-as-a-judge** (abstractive case).

- 1) **ROUGE-L** evaluates the overlap between the model's answer and the gold-standard abstractive answer. This metric measures the longest sequence of words shared between prediction and reference, after tokenization and optional stemming. Using the F1 variant balances precision and recall, reflecting both how much of the reference is captured and how much of the generated answer is relevant.
- 2) The **BERTScore (F1)** for the abstractive setting quantifies the semantic similarity between the model's abstractive answer and the reference using XLM-RoBERTa-large, a multilingual embedding model suitable for Spanish. Both texts are converted into contextual embeddings, and precision, recall and F1 are computed at the token level, with F1 retained as the main metric. BERTScore (F1) captures meaning preservation even

when the model rephrases content, uses synonyms or reorganizes information, providing a robust measure of semantic fidelity beyond exact wording.

- 3) For the **LLM-as-a-judge (Abstractive)**, we follow a similar approach to the extractive QA case, using a second LLM as an impartial judge. The judge reviews the dialogue, the question, and the model's answer, comparing it to the ground truth. In this case, it assigns a score from 1 to 5 based on correctness, absence of hallucination, and fidelity to implied meaning. Higher scores reflect nuanced understanding, while lower scores indicate shallow, incorrect or fabricated reasoning. This evaluation layer captures subtleties of meaning and reasoning that are not fully captured by lexical overlap or embedding-based metrics, providing a complementary perspective on answer quality. Again, we use the gemma-3-27b-it model from Google in a 4-bit quantized format.

The prompt used for the judge is:

```
Eres un juez de respuestas abstractivas.
```

```
Recibirás:
```

1. Una transcripción de un diálogo.
2. Una pregunta sobre el diálogo.
3. Una respuesta de referencia (Ground Truth) que refleja una interpretación correcta.
4. La respuesta propuesta por el usuario.

```
Tu tarea: Evaluar si la respuesta del usuario es una interpretación adecuada del diálogo, capturando el significado, las intenciones y la información relevante, sin inventar hechos que no estén implícitos en el diálogo.
```

```
Asigna una puntuación ENTERA entre 1 y 5 según estos criterios:
```

- 1: Totalmente incorrecta, inventada o contradice el diálogo.
- 2: Contiene algo correcto, pero omite aspectos clave o añade información no sustentada.
- 3: Parcialmente correcta, refleja parte del sentido pero con omisiones o errores.
- 4: Muy cercana a la interpretación correcta, con solo detalles menores faltantes.
- 5: Captura perfectamente la intención y el contenido del diálogo, sin errores ni añadidos.

```
Reglas estrictas:
```

- Evalúa la calidad interpretativa (no literal) de la respuesta.
- NO expliques tu decisión, NO añadas texto extra: devuelve SOLO un número entero (1-5).

```
Diálogo:
```

```
{{dialogue}}
```

```
{{example}}
```

```
Pregunta: {{question}}
```

```
Ground Truth: {{gt_answer}}
```

```
Respuesta del usuario: {{candidate_answer}}
```

```
Respuesta:
```

For the summarization task, we compute the same metrics as for abstractive QA. However, in this case, the prompts used for LLM-as-a-Judge are tailored for summarization and evaluate coverage of essential dialogue content, interpretative coherence, absence of hallucination, narrative consistency and informativeness. The judge, which is again gemma-3-27b-it, applies the same 1–5 scoring scale used for abstractive QA. This multilayered evaluation ensures that summaries are not only linguistically aligned with the reference but also conceptually faithful and informative.

The prompt used for the judge is:

Eres un juez encargado de evaluar resúmenes.

Recibirás:

- Una transcripción de un diálogo.
- Un resumen de referencia (Ground Truth) que representa una interpretación correcta, completa y coherente.
- El resumen generado por el usuario.

Tu tarea: Evaluar qué tan bien el resumen del usuario captura el contenido, la intención, el tono, los temas principales y la información implícita del diálogo, sin inventar hechos que no estén en la conversación.

Asigna una puntuación ENTERA entre 1 y 5 según estos criterios:

- 1: Totalmente incorrecto, irrelevante o inventado.
- 2: Contiene elementos correctos pero es muy incompleto, ambiguo o añade información no sustentada.
- 3: Abarca parte del contenido, pero con omisiones importantes o errores interpretativos.
- 4: Refleja con bastante fidelidad el diálogo, con solo detalles menores faltantes.
- 5: Resume con precisión y naturalidad todo lo esencial del diálogo, sin errores ni añadidos.

Reglas importantes:

- Evalúa la calidad global del resumen (interpretación, cobertura, fidelidad).
- NO expliques tu decisión, NO añadas texto extra: devuelve SOLO un número entero (1-5).

Diálogo:

{{dialogue}}

Ground Truth: {{gt_summary}}

Resumen del usuario: {{candidate_summary}}

Respuesta:

3.3.1.3 Results

Using the test set for Pilot 1, we have computed some initial results for three multilingual models (covering all 24 official European Union languages): Salamandra-2b-instruct, Salamandra-7b-instruct, EuroLLM-1.7B-Instruct, EuroLLM-9B-Instruct and Apertus-8B-Instruct-2509. Table 1 reports the metrics obtained:

Table 1 Results on Pilot 1 dataset

Model	Extractive QA					Abstractive QA			Summarization		
	Exact Match	Answer Coverage Score	BERTScore (F1)	LLM-as-a-judge	Answerability Accuracy	ROUGE-L	BERTScore (F1)	LLM-as-a-judge	ROUGE-L	BERTScore (F1)	LLM-as-a-judge
Salamandra-2b-instruct	0.146	0.3	0.885	1.999	0.710	0.169	0.899	3.319	0.160	0.879	2.4
Salamandra-7b-instruct	0.180	0.348	0.902	2.139	0.718	0.184	0.898	4.050	0.182	0.883	4
EuroLLM-1.7B-Instruct	0.138*	0.290*	0.877*	1.980*	0.698*	0.128*	0.867*	2.757*	0.145*	0.836*	2*
EuroLLM-9B-Instruct	0.202*	0.369*	0.895*	2.180*	0.833*	0.209*	0.893*	3.877*	0.218*	0.884*	3.2*
Apertus-8B-Instruct-2509	0.254	0.388	0.915	2.318	0.756	0.202	0.898	4.468	0.222	0.882	3.6

We obtained straightforward results for the EuroLLM models, but we marked them with an asterisk because these models can only process up to 4,096 tokens. In the last sample of the test set, the input exceeds this limit. As a result, the model’s output becomes unreliable, showing signs of hallucination and failing to properly answer the question. This issue appears across all questions involving the 5th conversation.

This highlights an important next step for the project: exploring strategies to handle long-context inputs effectively, either through context summarization or by using RAG-based techniques.

3.3.2 Pilot 4 Evaluation

The overall system architecture is presented in Figure 1. The dialogue involves two participants: human users on one side, typically parents of young children, and an intelligent support system on the other. The system has been designed to assist medical staff in providing timely and accurate advice related to preventive care, everyday situations, general inquiries, and, in certain cases, potential emergencies. Its primary role is to manage the initial interaction with the caller, collecting relevant information until a medical professional becomes available.

To minimise the risk of incorrect or misleading advice, the system adopts an active role in the dialogue. It guides the conversation through structured prompts, while the caller provides answers to specific questions. The gathered information is then used to produce a structured summary, which is automatically presented to the medical professional upon their involvement.

In situations where a human agent is not immediately available, the system can retrieve relevant responses from a curated external dataset. If a suitable entry is found, the corresponding text is delivered to the caller; otherwise, no response is provided. Importantly, the system does not generate new or speculative content since it operates exclusively with verified information extracted from the established medical knowledge base.

The work regarding Pilot 4, described in Sections 0, 3.4.2, 4.4.2, 4.4.3, focuses primarily on the mechanisms for extracting and utilizing content from the external data source.

Figure 1 UNS pilot architecture

3.3.2.1 External data source

The external data used within the Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) framework needed to be both reliable and contextually appropriate. At the same time, the selected content had to be accessible to a general audience, not limited to domain experts. To meet these criteria, textual material was collected from online healthcare portals focused on infant care. After a comprehensive review of multiple sources, four portals were identified as the most suitable. Each explicitly stated that its content had been prepared or reviewed by qualified medical professionals.

An additional validation step was performed by independent medical experts, who confirmed the accuracy and suitability of selected materials. Specifically, three medical experts were presented with a randomly selected subset of texts and asked to assess their factual correctness and medical faithfulness. Once the selection was finalised and written consent for scientific use obtained, automated data extraction and textual preprocessing were carried out. The resulting dataset contains approximately 4,000 documents, systematically organized into several thematic categories. It should be noted that created dataset doesn't contain any confidential data. There are no patient records or any other personal information.

3.3.2.2 Input dialogues

Since the system is tailored for a scenario in which only questions are permitted and no comparable resources currently exist, a dedicated dataset was created. For this purpose, a dialogue collection was conducted in collaboration with medical experts. The resulting multimodal corpus comprises 150 acted dialogues in Serbian, based on loosely predefined scripts, accompanied by corresponding transcriptions. Each dialogue includes a concise summary (e.g., "1-year-old child, temperature 39°C, cough and sore throat").

For evaluation, a random subset of 10 dialogues was selected. The system does not use full transcripts as input but instead relies on dialogue summaries. Within the RAG framework, the five most relevant text snippets are retrieved based on cosine similarity scores.

3.3.2.3 Retrieval details

After creating the external dataset, all textual documents were converted into 1,024-dimensional embeddings using the OpenAI embedding model. These embeddings were indexed using FAISS³, a vector database optimised for efficient similarity search over large datasets.

Upon receiving a user query, the system generates its embedding with the same model and performs an approximate k-nearest neighbour (k-NN) search over the FAISS index. Cosine similarity is then used to rank the retrieved documents.

3.3.2.4 Automatic evaluation

The automatic evaluation of the appropriateness of generated content is based on direct or implicit usage of LLM-as-a-judge. In direct approach, LLM was prompted to score the input summary appropriateness to the snippets from the external dataset. The LLM was prompted to generate a score on the Likert scale (Likert 1932).

In addition to using an LLM directly to evaluate the relevance and appropriateness of generated answers with respect to the input summaries, we also experimented with an adaptation of the FactScore metric (Min 2023), adjusted for our specific scenario. As each input summary is structured as bullet-point, each bullet point can be systematically verified for its presence in the generated response. The FactScore for a given input is then computed as:

$$f(y) = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{A}_y|} \sum_{a \in \mathcal{A}_y} [a \text{ is supported by } y],$$

where \mathcal{A}_y represents the set of all summary bullet points (summary ground truth) and y is the generated answer. In proposed automatic approach LLM is used for checking if some fact is contained in the generated text.

Furthermore, we introduced a more flexible automatic evaluation method. Instead of assigning a strict binary (true/false) score to each bullet point, evaluators were asked to rate the degree to which each bullet point was supported by the generated text using a 5-point Likert scale. The final score for each input was then calculated as the average rating across all bullet points:

$$f(y) = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{A}_y|} \sum_{a \in \mathcal{A}_y} [LS(a)],$$

where \mathcal{A}_y is the set of all summary bullet points and $LS(a)$ is Likert score of given fact a . For all automatic scoring procedures, ChatGPT-4o-mini was used as the underlying LLM. The results are summarised in Table , which presents two types of scores: (1) the average LLM score across all five retrieved snippets for single input and (2) the best individual score generated by the LLM for any of the five retrieved snippets for a single input.

Analysis of the LLM-as-a-judge results (in Table 2) indicates that the relatively modest average scores reflect that the generated snippets are not consistently well aligned with the corresponding summaries. However, if for a given input, there is a retrieved snippet with an LLM score of 3 or higher, it indicates that this snippet represents a reasonably good match. Conversely, for inputs S6, S9, and S10, both the low average and best scores point to a generally low level of appropriateness across all retrieved snippets.

The overall results of **FactScore** and **FactScore-Likert**, compared with the **LLM-as-a-judge** evaluation, reveal notable inconsistencies. For instance, **S3** attains an acceptable best LLM score (3), whereas **S10** does not (best LLM score = 1); nevertheless, their corresponding **FactScore/FactScore-Likert** average values are comparable. This indicates that the automatic metrics may not reliably discriminate between clearly acceptable and clearly unacceptable cases, at least for some inputs. A closer inspection further shows that, within the **FactScore-Likert** variant, the snippet with the best LLM score for a given input is consistently the top-ranked snippet by this metric—an alignment

³ <https://github.com/facebookresearch/faiss>

that does **not** always hold for the binary **FactScore**. For example, when using summary **S5** as input, the snippet with the highest **FactScore** achieves a value of 0.24. However, this snippet differs from the one identified as best by both the human evaluators and the LLM. The snippet ranked highest by these two metrics receives a **FactScore** of only 0.05, illustrating the poor alignment between the binary FactScore metric and human or LLM-based judgments. This pattern is reflected in the correlations computed over all 50 generated outputs 0.24 for FactScore versus 0.57 for FactScore-Likert with the LLM-as-a-judge scores, suggesting that the Likert-based approach better captures graded, partial support present in the generated texts.

Table 2 UNS Pilot automatic evaluation results

Group	Measure	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	S7	S8	S9	S10
LLM-as-a-judge	Average	1.4	1.8	1.4	2.6	2.6	1.4	2.2	2.6	1.0	1.0
	Best	3.0	3.0	3.0	4.0	4.0	2.0	5.0	4.0	1.0	1.0
FactScore	Average	0.2	0.07	0.11	0.43	0.08	0.11	0.06	0.02	0.13	0.1
	Best	0.08	0.17	0.11	0.46	0.24	0.18	0.3	0.1	0.22	0.25
FactScore Likert	Average	1.8	1.81	1.98	2.7	2.13	2.25	2.08	2.12	1.84	1.91
	Best	1.92	1.83	2.22	3.15	2.70	2.45	2.70	2.70	2.11	2.33

3.4 Correlation with human judgement

3.4.1 Fused dataset – BUL

The scope of this evaluation covers faithfulness evaluation for dialogue summarisation, as well as question-answering domains, with human judgements for LLM responses being provided within the ELOQUENCE fused dataset for these domains. Additional domains are covered within the ELOQUENCE fused dataset, such as Task-Oriented Dialogues and Machine Translation, but these are less relevant to the production of faithfulness and explainability metrics and so are excluded from the following evaluation.

3.4.1.1 General Question Answering

Common metrics for QA faithfulness evaluation are calculated using the short-form and long-form answers and responses, as well as for short-form and long-form fact-tuples. Two LLM metrics are trialled, the LLM Likert approach which prompts the model to output a faithfulness score between 0 and 5, with 0 representing complete unfaithfulness and 5 representing perfect alignment between the ground-truth and the response. The second LLM metric assessed is LLM Conf., which prompts the model to output a binary faithfulness score, which is then reduced by the token logits in the case of a faithful prediction or increased for an unfaithful prediction. This provides additional granularity for faithfulness through utilising the probability of the classification.

We find that the long-form QA task to favour the LLM confidence approach, whilst the short-form evaluation favours the Likert approach.

The Pearson correlations attained for both long-form and short-form QA approaches are detailed in

Table 3. Across most metrics, short-form evaluation produces higher correlations than their long-form counterparts. This is to be expected and is likely a large reason why QA faithfulness evaluation typically utilizes these short-form datasets. The highest correlation attained overall is found using the short-form domain, when using the LLM Likert approach, with a correlation of 0.831.

We observe that the graph-based metrics perform comparably to n-gram strategies for long-form evaluation. However, they do not attain any strong correlations for short-form, despite the Unlabelled F1 mean metric attaining a significant p-value.

Table 3 Question Answering Correlations with human judgement

Metric	Metric Classification					Short-Form		Long-Form	
	LLM	N-gram	Graph	Embedding	Matching	Human Likert	Human Bool	Human Likert	Human Bool
LLM Likert	X					0.815***	0.783***	0.658***	0.642***
LLM Conf.	X					0.729***	0.728***	0.659***	0.637***
ROUGE-1		X				0.629***	0.617***	0.235*	0.191
ROUGE-L		X				0.623***	0.608***	0.240*	0.189
BERTScore				X		0.502***	0.500***	0.378***	0.350***
Lexical match					X	0.457***	0.427***	0.388***	0.357***
ROUGE-2		X				0.451***	0.434***	0.277**	0.228*
Unlabelled F1 mean			X			0.203*	0.223*	0.245*	0.228*
SMATCH mean			X			0.183	0.191	0.228*	0.195
No WSD F1 mean			X			0.182	0.191	0.231*	0.200*
Unlabelled F1 min			X			0.178	0.195	0.224*	0.210*
SMATCH max			X			0.176	0.185	0.238*	0.200*
No WSD F1 max			X			0.174	0.183	0.244*	0.210*
Unlabelled F1 max			X			0.172	0.192	0.257**	0.238*
Exact match					X	0.161	0.171	N/A	N/A
SMATCH min			X			0.154	0.160	0.214*	0.186
No WSD F1 min			X			0.153	0.159	0.213*	0.187
Entity F1 max			X			-0.127	-0.127	-0.066	-0.112
Entity F1 mean			X			-0.086	-0.078	-0.092	-0.141
Entity F1 min			X			-0.057	-0.045	-0.111	-0.161

Note: Correlations with $P \leq 0.05$, $P \leq 0.01$ and $P < 0.001$ are marked *, ** and *** respectively.

3.4.1.2 Extractive QA

The conversational QA domain functions similarly to the QA domain outlined previously. The primary difference is the incorporation of context within the prompt, taking the form of inputting the entire dialogue history prior to the question. This provision of context within the prompt makes this task comparable to a reading comprehension task. These LLM responses are then appended to the fused dataset for the metrics to be calculated and incorporated, including LLM-as-a-judge approaches. The human judgements that are gathered for this domain are produced in the same manner as with the previous QA task.

We find the LLM-as-a-judge confidence approach to be the most highly correlated with human judgement, with a significant decline in performance for other metrics. However, the LLM confidence approach also significantly outperforms the LLM Likert approach.

The correlations attained for the conversational QA domain are detailed below in Table 4.

Table 4 Conversational QA correlations with human judgement

Metric	Metric Classification					Human Likert	Human Bool
	LLM	N-gram	Graph	Embedding	Matching		
Lexical match					X	0.461***	0.429***
LLM Conf.	X					0.427***	0.453***
ROUGE-1	X					0.403***	0.377***
ROUGE-L		X				0.399***	0.374***
ROUGE-2		X				0.285**	0.270**
BERTScore				X		0.272**	0.268**
LLM Likert					X	0.232*	0.213*
Unlabeled F1		X				0.199	0.188
SMATCH			X			0.192	0.182
No WSD F1			X			0.191	0.181
Entity F1			X			0.068	0.053
Exact match			X			0.052	0.046

Note: Correlations with $P \leq 0.05$, $P \leq 0.01$ and $P < 0.001$ are marked *, ** and *** respectively.

3.4.1.3 Dialogue Summarisation

Prompting the LLM to produce summarised points from the multi-turn dialogue and evaluating these responses against the ground truth summary as well as the full dialogue transcript is conducted for the evaluation of faithfulness.

The SAMSum (Gliwa 2019) dataset has been selected for use in this faithfulness evaluation. The LLM-as-a-judge techniques are aligned with the previously used methodologies, relating to the Likert prompting approach and the use of token confidence to influence the faithfulness score.

For evaluating against the ground truth, this is conducted in a pairwise manner, whereby the generated summarised points are evaluated against the extracted ground-truth summarised points, with the highest scoring match being determined to be the paired summary point. This provides a score for each summary point made by the LLM, which are then used to calculate mean, maximum and minimum scores for each metric. This is considered the "fact"-based approach. This technique was developed through inspiration from (Min 2023) with their FACTScore approach, see Section 3.3.2.4, which has been demonstrated in the literature to improve correlation with human judgement compared to long-form comparison (Min 2023).

This contrasts the "Full" approach, whereby the LLM judgement is produced to cover all summarised points. Additional metrics were trialled for the graph-based approaches, with graphs being generated for each dialogue turn (to be evaluated in a pairwise manner with both the transcript, as well as the ground truth summaries), as well as graphs being evaluated using the full transcript graph.

Additionally, metrics have been calculated using the full dialogue transcript for the LLM and graph-based metrics - due to their capability in assessing long-form text.

The correlations attained for both ground truth evaluation and transcript strategies are detailed below in Table 5. Due to the additional range of metrics computed for this domain, only positively correlated metrics are included within the table.

We find the best-performing metric to be the LLM Likert approach that utilises a faithfulness scoring for each generated summary (the "fact"-based approach), with the overall score being determined by the least faithful point. This is likely due to the generally prevalence for LLMs to overestimate faithfulness, which can attribute too much importance to an average score. The use of this "fact"-based approach significantly outperforms the use of LLM's to score all the summarised points. However, this could be because the human evaluations have been gathered in a similar way, with correlations being calculated against the mean human judgement for all LLM summaries. It is of

note that when the correlations are calculated using the human Boolean mean (with Likert scores of three or more being considered faithful, and the average taken for all judgements) that the correlations are significantly weaker, with very few significant correlations being identified.

Table 5 Dialogue summarisation correlations with human judgement

Metric	Metric Classification					Human Likert mean	Human Bool mean
	LLM	N-gram	Graph	Embedding	Matching		
LLM Conf. Fact mean	X					0.578***	0.380***
LLM Conf. Fact min	X					0.573***	0.415***
LLM Likert Fact mean	X					0.465***	0.264**
LLM Likert Fact min	X					0.409***	0.322**
BERTScore mean				X		0.221*	0.135
BERTScore max				X		0.199*	0.143
LLM Likert	X					0.164	0.023
Transcript Unlabeled F1			X			0.164	0.149
Transcript SMATCH			X			0.150	0.149
ROUGE-2 mean		X				0.148	0.090
ROUGE-2 max		X				0.140	0.059
Turn GT SMATCH			X			0.136	0.159
BERTScore min				X		0.136	0.055
ROUGE-L max		X				0.128	0.088
Turn GT Unlabeled F1			X			0.127	0.148

Note: Correlations with $P \leq 0.05$, $P \leq 0.01$ and $P < 0.001$ are marked *, ** and *** respectively.

3.4.2 Pilot 4 Dataset – UNS

For the given system, there are no definitive ground-truth answers, as multiple generated snippets may be equally appropriate depending on the specific context. Consequently, the only reliable way to assess the appropriateness of generated content is through human evaluation.

To ensure that the system’s responses are both trustworthy and understandable to non-expert users, an evaluation was conducted with two distinct participant groups. The first group comprised ten non-experts with practical experience in child upbringing, recruited among the UNS employees, while the second group consisted of two domain experts—medical nurses specializing in infant and child healthcare. In the non-expert group, there were four female participants aged 32–42 years and six male participants aged 30–48 years. Medical nurses were aged 50–60 years. Participants were presented with input summaries together with the corresponding RAG-generated outputs, as discussed in section 3.3.2.3. For each generated text (50 in total), they rated its appropriateness on a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (completely inappropriate) to 5 (highly appropriate).

The Likert scale was selected because it is one of the most widely adopted methods for capturing subjective human judgments in natural language processing evaluations, offering simplicity for annotators and reliable quantitative measures for analysis (Likert 1932).

Table 6 UNS Pilot expert evaluation results

Group	Measure	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	S7	S8	S9	S10
Experts	Average	1.9	2.2	2.2	3.2	2.9	1.3	2.8	2.7	1.2	1.2
	Best	3.0	3.5	3.5	4.0	3.5	1.5	5.0	4.0	2.0	2.0
Non-experts	Average	2.17	1.86	2.37	3.4	3.03	1.2	2.31	2.69	1.0	1.03
	Best	3.86	2.43	4.43	4.71	3.86	1.3	3.9	4.1	1.0	1.14

The evaluation results are summarised in Table 6. As in Table 2 (Section 3.3.2.4), the values labelled as average in Table 6 represent the mean human evaluation score across the five documents retrieved for a given input, while best refers to the highest-rated document for that input, averaged across evaluators. Notably, in half of the cases (5 out of 10 inputs), the document ranked highest by the RAG did not correspond to the one receiving the highest human rating. This discrepancy highlights the importance of incorporating re-scoring mechanisms to better align system outputs with human judgment.

Across all evaluated examples, the same document was consistently identified as the best by both experts and non-experts, demonstrating a high degree of overlap in their assessments. Although the average per-input scores were sometimes modest, the best scores were generally strong, as seen in cases such as S1 and S3, where both groups rated the top outputs positively. The Pearson correlation coefficient between expert and non-expert ratings was 0.78, indicating a strong agreement and suggesting that the system achieves a satisfactory balance between factual reliability and usability for non-expert audiences.

Conversely, consistently low scores—both average and best—across both evaluator groups (e.g. S6, S9, and S10) indicate the generation of inadequate or inappropriate responses, which should be excluded from user presentation. A closer inspection revealed that such low-quality outputs typically relate to topics insufficiently represented in the external dataset, emphasizing the need for further dataset enrichment in these areas.

To further examine the relationship between automatic and human evaluations, Pearson correlation coefficients were computed between the proposed automatic metrics and human judgments, as presented in Table 7.

The results indicate that the most effective evaluation strategy is achieved by directly prompting the LLM to assess the appropriateness of generated texts with respect to the given inputs. In all examined cases, the document identified as best by human evaluators was also consistently selected as best by the LLM-based scoring method.

In contrast, the binary FactScore variant exhibited weak correlation with human ratings, indicating limited suitability for this task. The modified FactScoreLikert approach, which applies graded Likert-scale values to individual bullet points, produced slightly better alignment but still lagged the direct LLM-based evaluation, which remained the most reliable indicator of perceived appropriateness.

Table 7 UNS pilot expert evaluation Pearson correlation to automatic evaluation

Metric	Expert	Non-expert
LLM-as-a-judge	0.80***	0.82***
LLM FactScore	0.22	0.29**
LLM FactScoreLikert	0.55***	r(48)=0.53***

Note: Correlations with $P \leq 0.05$, $P \leq 0.01$ and $P < 0.001$ are marked *, ** and *** respectively.

3.5 Conclusion

When evaluating the faithfulness across both the ELOQUENCE fused dataset as well as the Pilot 4 dataset, we observe strong performance from LLM-as-a-judge techniques, with strong correlations with human judgement. However, the optimal implementation of the LLM-as-a-judge metric differs across the domains and tasks with which it has been implemented, with a Likert-based approach demonstrating the strongest correlations in the QA tasks within the fused dataset, yet it displayed weaker correlations than the baseline LLM-as-a-judge approach for the Pilot 4 data. However, it is worth noting that this was also using the FactScore methodology, and the use of the Likert ratings did improve upon the FactScore baseline.

Human evaluation in Pilot 4 revealed strong agreement between expert and non-expert annotators, with a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.78. For Pilot 4, FactScore-Likert demonstrated a substantially higher correlation with LLM-as-a-judge scores (0.57) compared to the binary FactScore baseline (0.24). In Pilot 1, the Salamandra-7b-instruct model outperformed all tested models in LLM-as-a-judge evaluations for the dialogue Summarization task (4.00). The Apertus-8B-Instruct-2509 model reported the LLM-as-a-judge higher mean scores in Extractive Question Answering (2.32) and Abstractive Question Answering (4.47).

Within the ELOQUENCE fused dataset's General Question Answering domain, the strongest correlation with human judgement was 0.831, achieved by the LLM Likert approach for Short-Form Question Answering. For Long-Form Question Answering, graph-based metrics performed on par with traditional n-gram-based strategies, whereas for Short-Form Question Answering they exhibited no statistically significant correlation with human judgements. In dialogue summarisation, the LLM Likert approach using the minimum score across factual units (the "fact"-based minimum strategy) performed best, reaching a correlation of 0.636 with human evaluations. Across domains in the fused dataset evaluation, the LLM Confidence approach (transforming binary faithfulness predictions into continuous scores using token-level logits) was frequently the top-performing metric and was generally preferred for Long-Form Question Answering.

4 Explainability evaluation

4.1 Introduction

As presented in (Doshi-Velez y Kim 2017), explainability or interpretability in the domain of machine learning refers to a model's ability to clarify or justify its predictions in terms understandable to humans. By providing such explanations, models foster greater user trust and promote their wider adoption in everyday applications.

According to (Molnar 2018), there are two main types of interpretabilities, distinguished by the stage at which interpretability is achieved. *Intrinsic interpretability* is obtained by designing models that are inherently self-explanatory, embedding interpretability directly into their structure. In contrast, *post-hoc interpretability* involves developing a separate explanatory model to interpret or justify the behaviour of an already trained model.

The authors in (Du, Liu y Hu 2019) further refined this classification by introducing the notions of global and local explainability. Global interpretability enables users to understand how a model operates by analysing its overall structure, parameters, and internal representations; explaining, for example, what linguistic or conceptual information is captured by individual neurons, hidden layers, or other architectural components (Zhao y et al. 2024). Local interpretability, on the other hand, focuses on individual predictions, aiming to explain why a model produced a specific decision or output (Du, Liu y Hu 2019).

4.2 Graph-based evaluation

4.2.1 Graph-based evaluation for question answering and summarization

Abstract Meaning Representation (AMR) is a way text can be encoded to produce a graph, whereby entities and relationships are extracted, forming nodes and edges respectively (Banarescu, et al. 2013). This technique is aligned with explainability due to the compartmentalisation of key information in an easily interpretable and visual manner. For the assessment of graph generation approaches we have used STOG BART Large ⁴, a BART model trained on the AMR-3 dataset. This technique is only trialled for the QA and dialogue summarisation domains (present within the ELOQUENCE fused dataset), as TOD already utilises highly structured data and thus is less suitable for this approach.

For QA, the reference graphs are generated using both long-form and short-form ground truth answers and are evaluated against the long-form and short-form LLM responses to each question. For dialogue summarisation, reference graphs are generated using both the full dialogue history, as well as the ground truth summaries. These graphs are then evaluated against the LLM-generated summary graphs.

The metrics used for the graph evaluation are the same for both domains, with SMatch (Cai and Knight 2013) being calculated across all evaluations. However, SMatch scores are calculated with additional configurations also - such as F1 score for named entities (Entity F1), the removal of Word-Sense-Disambiguation (No WSD F1) and the calculation of F1 without relationship labels being necessitated (Unlabelled F1). These additional metrics allow for greater scope of evaluation. The results from this graph-based evaluation is located in section 3.4.1, as the metrics derived from the AMR graph generation is measuring faithfulness – despite the graphs themselves conveying additional explainability.

Figure has been generated from the SAMSum (Gliwa 2019) subset of the fused dataset and conveys the original summary text: 'Aria has just run into Charlie Evans.'

Figure has been generated from the Natural Questions (Kwiatkowski 2019) subset using the ground truth short-form answer: 'Coldplay with special guest performers Beyonce and Bruno Mars'

⁴ <https://github.com/bjascob/amr-lib-models>

Figure 2 SAMSum AMR excerpt

Figure 3 Natural Questions AMR excerpt

4.2.2 Conversational modelling through graphs

The goal of conversational modelling through graphs is to analyse and interpret the underlying structure of dialogues, a technique that is especially relevant in high-risk settings where system responses must follow verifiable interaction patterns. This approach leverages the Dialog2Flow (D2F) framework introduced in [Deliverable 3.1](#), which automatically extracts structured dialogue flows from unstructured dialogue data, either semi- or fully automatically. The methodology follows three steps:

1. **Extraction of Raw Graphs:** As described in [Deliverable 3.1](#), using the D2F embeddings, we cluster the embeddings of all the utterances in the dialogues and construct a weighted action (cluster) transition graph. This graph represents the typical conversational trajectories by encapsulating the functional intent (dialogue acts) and task-specific information (slots) of an utterance into a cohesive dialogue action. The resulting graphs reveal the common flow of conversations with a degree of detail. After this stage, the nodes of the graph do not have a label, since each represents a cluster of utterances, making it hard to be interpreted.
2. **LLM-based Node Labelling:** Once the raw graph is extracted in the previous step, an LLM is used to generate descriptive labels for each node. This labelling process is based on providing the top-k utterances contained within each specific cluster/node to the LLM and asked to provide a short and meaningful label for it. For instance, a generated graph from the "hospital" domain shown in [Deliverable 3.1](#) (Figure 5.4) will look like the Figure 4 shown on the right, after this node label stage.
3. **Comparison of Reference vs. System Graphs:** The extracted dialogue flows function as evaluation scaffolds for assessing the faithfulness and coherence of LLM-generated dialogues. This involves a manual comparison between a reference graph (derived from real human, in-domain conversations) and a system graph (generated from system-generated dialogues). This comparison helps identify whether the generated conversations adhere to coherent patterns or deviate unpredictably, serving as a powerful tool for system evaluation and debugging. For instance, in the context of Pilot 4 (NurseLLM), D2F could audit AI-assistant interactions to ensure adherence to customer support protocols.

Figure 4. Graph after node labeling stage

This analytical process of conversational modelling through graphs is implemented in the latest version of the **SDialog** Python library, which was introduced in Chapter 5 of [Deliverable 2.3](#). SDialog⁵ (Idiap Research Group 2025) provides a modular and extensible framework that supports synthetic dialogue generation and analysis.

⁵ <https://github.com/idiap/sdialog>

4.3 LLM-based evaluation

The explainability of LLM outputs is a highly diverse field, encompassing numerous approaches to produce human-interpretable results (Zhao and et al. 2024) . These methods range from LLMs generating natural language explanations to RAG systems providing document similarity scores (J. Burton 2023, R. Friel 2024).

Due to the desirability of eMetrics, a fused metric detailing a combined score to represent trustworthiness and explainability, it is important to obtain a numerical score that can be associated with explainability – similarly to the process performed for faithfulness. For RAG applications, there are additional metrics that can be incorporated (and have been implemented in other studies (J. Burton 2023, Zhao and et al. 2024, R. Friel 2024)). However, outside of RAG use cases, there is little in the way of standardised approaches to measure explainability numerically. Due to this, we have opted to trial several metrics that have been utilised in previous studies on the ELOQUENCE fused dataset. The metrics that we are experimentally evaluating for the purpose of measuring explainability can be defined as LLM-based and RAG-based.

The LLM-based metrics used to measure the explainability of LLM outputs are comparable to the LLM-as-a-judge techniques employed for faithfulness evaluation. However, to measure explainability we also prompt the LLM to output a natural language explanation of the previous LLM response, as demonstrated by (J. Burton 2023). This is then converted into a Likert score, as well as a continuous score (between 0 and 1) using the token logits – as discussed in section 3.2.3.1. These metrics thus provide a numerical value representing the faithfulness of the LLM explanation. Whereas the RAG-based metrics provide representations of explainability through reference to the external knowledge source. For our tests, we use the cosine similarity between the LLM input and the retrieved document as a measure of explainability, as this represents how well aligned the document is to the query. We also use precision@k, a metric which gives the placement of the gold value, whereby a score of 1 means that the top result (for our RAG pipeline, this represents the most similar document) is the gold value.

For producing explainable outputs and metrics, we use the Natural Questions (Kwiatkowski 2019) subset of the ELOQUENCE fused dataset and produce a vector database using the sources that are present. These sources comprise Wikipedia pages which are then scraped to produce a document per paragraph and embedded (using BGE embeddings⁶) to form a vector database for the RAG evaluation pipeline.

We calculate Pearson correlation coefficients for the explainability metrics that are produced against the previously used faithfulness metrics, attempting to confirm that the explainability metrics convey novel information and are not a simulacrum of the faithfulness metrics. This analysis is displayed below in Table 8, where we observe that there are no strong correlations between explainable metrics and faithfulness metrics – which provides confidence that they are distinct from one another. The top 5 documents (representing paragraphs from the source) are retrieved, with these 5 documents the RAG-based metrics are calculated, covering the minimums and means across the 5 documents. Whilst the LLM-based explainability approaches only focus on the top-1 document. Additionally, Table 9 is produced which shows the means and standard deviations for each assessed metric, where “exp.” refers to an explainability metric and “faith.” refers to a faithfulness metric. We observe that the LLM-based explainability metrics fare more consistently than the LLM-based faithfulness metrics, with significantly lower standard deviations and means that are closer to the maximum values.

⁶ <https://huggingface.co/BAAI/bge-large-en>

Table 8 Explainability correlations

	LLM Conf. (explainability)	LLM Likert (faithfulness)	LLM Conf. (faithfulness)	LLM Likert (explainability)	Distance mean (explainability)	Distance max (explainability)	Distance min (explainability)
LLM Conf. (explainability)	1						
LLM Likert (faithfulness)	0.126**	1.000					
LLM Conf. (faithfulness)	0.108*	0.853***	1.000				
LLM Likert (explainability)	0.792***	0.098	0.088	1.000			
Distance mean (explainability)	-0.100*	-0.179***	-0.112*	-0.135***	1.000		
Distance max (explainability)	-0.014	-0.142**	-0.074	-0.053	0.932***	1.000	
Distance min (explainability)	-0.255***	-0.171***	-0.138**	-0.262***	0.762***	0.549***	1.000
k mean (explainability)	-0.242***	0.002	-0.031	-0.290***	0.001	-0.052	0.117**

Note: Correlations with $P \leq 0.05$, $P \leq 0.01$ and $P < 0.001$ are marked *, ** and *** respectively.

Table 9 Explainability statistics

	LLM Conf. (exp.)	LLM Likert (faith.)	LLM Conf. (faith.)	LLM Likert (exp.)	Distance mean (exp.)	Distance max (exp.)	Distance min (exp.)	k mean (exp.)
Mean	0.903	4.034	0.838	4.774	0.797	0.881	0.662	1.082
Std. Dev	0.271	1.297	0.349	0.606	0.107	0.115	0.120	0.370

4.4 Pilot Evaluations

4.4.1 Readability and lexicographical metrics using Pilot 2

We use a set of readability metrics to assess how clear and understandable a sentence or a period is. The underlying assumption is that, in a dialogue, both speakers should communicate using similar levels of complexity and should exchange messages that are statistically similar according to the complexity metrics. When a speaker uses long and articulated sentences while the other person responds with short, simple ones, the conversation may become unbalanced and less effective. In such cases, the second speaker may not capture the entire information provided by the first speaker. Analysing the readability metrics for each speaker's sentences provides a set of values indicating if the communication is balanced or not.

The following metrics were aimed at analysing text passages and were not conceived for dialogue analysis in the first attempt, notwithstanding they can provide useful indication also in dialogues. Analysis of the length of the sentences, the presence of long and complex words is a common trait and, similarly, for dialogues they can give hints on what's happening in the dialogue.

Readability metrics were initially conceived as first attempts to select suitable science textbooks for high school students (DuBay 2004). Several influential readability formulas emerged, such as the Flesch–Kincaid Grade Level (Thomas, Hartley y Kincaid 1975), Gunning Fog Index (Gunning 1952), SMOG Index (McLaughlin 1969), Coleman–Liau Index (Coleman y Liau 1975), and Automated Readability Index (Smith and Sender 1967). Most of these models use a linear function that considers few variables (typically two or three) and are based on simple linguistic features related to word or sentence characteristics (Feng, Jansche y Elhadad 2010). Although these methods have some known limitations, both the FRE and FKRLG formulas remain two of the most popular and accessible tools for assessing text readability (Ley y Florio 1996). Here are listed some of them with a detailed description.

4.4.1.1 The Flesch-Kincaid (F-K) score

The Flesch-Kincaid (F-K) scores are among the most widely used readability formulas in the world. Their development was driven by a need for objective, quantifiable measures of text difficulty. It was developed by Rudolf Flesch in the paper (Flesch 1948) where he argued that existing readability formulas were too complex. He proposed a new formula based on two core variables, average sentence length (in words) and Average word length (in syllables). His research correlated these factors with comprehension scores from reading tests to validate the formula. The resulting "Reading Ease" score was designed on a scale from 0 (very difficult) to 100 (very easy). The equation for the FK score is

$$FK = 0.39 \cdot \left(\frac{\text{words}}{\text{sentences}}\right) + 11.8 \cdot \left(\frac{\text{syllables}}{\text{words}}\right) - 15.59.$$

It considers the Average Sentence Length and the Average Number of Syllables per Word. Shorter sentences generally contribute to better readability. Furthermore, words with fewer syllables are considered easier to understand. The drawbacks of Flesch-Kincaid score are typically referred to multiple aspects. It does not measure meaning as the formula only counts syllables and sentences. A text can be complete nonsense but still get a "good" score if it uses short words and sentences. Vocabulary and context are ignored. The metric does not consider whether the words used are familiar to the reader or if the concepts are complex. A text about advanced physics will be hard, even with short words. The metric is language specific, and it was designed specifically for English. The relationship between syllables and readability is different in other languages. Also, its implementation is not simple as Syllable Counting can be tricky. While generally accurate, automated syllable counters can sometimes make mistakes with complex words.

4.4.1.2 The Gunning Fog Index

The Gunning Fog Index (Gunning 1952) is a readability test designed to estimate the years of formal education a reader needs to understand a text on the first reading. Like the Flesch-Kincaid, it is based on the premise that sentence length and word complexity are key drivers of reading difficulty. Its unique characteristic is that it specifically measures what its creator, Robert Gunning, a writing consultant who worked with newspapers and publishers, considered important for clear communication¹⁰. He argued that "fog" in writing is not a mark of intelligence but of poor communication. He used the index as a concrete tool for writers to self-diagnose and simplify their prose. The Gunning Fog Index is best used as a quick, initial check rather than a definitive measure of a text's comprehensibility. The Fog Index formula is:

$$FogIndex = 0.4 \cdot \left[\frac{\text{Words}}{\text{Sentences}} + 100 \frac{\text{Complex Words}}{\text{Words}} \right].$$

Words / Sentences indicated the average sentence length. Complex Words measures the percentage of words that have three or more syllables. However, there are critical exceptions. For example, proper nouns (e.g., "California," "Microsoft") are not counted as complex. Compound words (e.g., "bookkeeper") are not counted as complex. Easy-to-understand verbs that end in "-ed" or "-es" (e.g., "created," "passes") are often excluded. A Fog Index of 12, for example, means a reader with 12 years of education (a high school senior in the U.S.) should be able to understand the text. Generally, a score above 18 is considered unreadable, while scores for popular media often aim for 8 or lower.

4.4.1.3 The Coleman-Liau Index

The Coleman-Liau Index (Coleman y Liau 1975) is a readability test designed to estimate the U.S. grade level required to understand a text. Its key distinguishing feature is that it relies entirely on characters per words and sentences per words, deliberately avoiding the syllable and word-length counts that define other formulas such as Flesch-Kincaid and Gunning Fog. The developers, M. Coleman and T. L. Liau argued that character count is a more objective and efficient measure for computerized readability analysis, as it is easier to program and avoids the ambiguities of syllable counting. The most common form of the Coleman-Liau Index is:

$$\text{Coleman} - \text{Liau Index} = 0.0588 \cdot L - 0.296 \cdot S - 15.8,$$

where L is the average number of characters per 100 words. S is the average number of sentences per 100 words. Like the Flesch-Kincaid Grade Level, the output is a number that corresponds to a U.S. grade level. A score of 10.5 means a student in the middle of 10th grade should be able to understand the text. Like all readability formulas, the Coleman-Liau Index has been subject to criticism, and its limitations have been documented. One of them is the oversimplification of Linguistic Complexity: The formula reduces the complex cognitive process of reading to two surface-level text features. It does not account for vocabulary difficulty, syntax, coherence, or a reader's prior knowledge. A study demonstrates the limitations of traditional formulas like Coleman-Liau (Coleman y Liau 1975). The authors show that NLP tools measuring lexical sophistication (e.g., word frequency, concreteness) and syntactic complexity are more accurate predictors of text difficulty than classic metrics based on word and sentence length. This research underpins the argument for moving beyond formulas like Coleman-Liau for a more nuanced analysis.

4.4.1.4 The Linsear Write Readability Formula

The Linsear Write Formula (O'Hayre 1966) is a readability metric specifically developed for the United States Air Force to evaluate the clarity of technical manuals. Its unique characteristic is that it is a "recursive" formula, designed to be calculated manually with pencil and paper, making it easy for writers to use as they draft and edit text. Unlike automated formulas, Linsear Write requires a specific process and is tuned on a 100-word sample from the text. Each *easy word* (words of 2 syllables or less) counts as 1 point. Each *hard word* (words of 3 or more syllables) is counted as 3 points. The sheer score is adjusted with ad hoc rules, i.e., if the calculated score is greater than 20, divide the total by 2. If the calculated score is 20 or less, divide the total by 2 and then subtract 1. The simplified formula is given by

$$\text{Linsear Write simplified} = \frac{\text{Easy Words} + 3 \cdot \text{Hard Words}}{\text{Number of Sentences}},$$

followed by the adjustment rules. Linsear Write was developed by John O' Hayre, who worked for the U.S. Bureau of Land Management, and its most prominent promotion came from the U.S. Air Force, which needed to ensure its technical manuals were comprehensible. While the original Air Force manual (O'Hayre 1966) is a government document rather than a peer-reviewed journal article, it is the primary reference for the formula's implementation and purpose. Its influence has been widely documented in readability literature.

4.4.1.5 The Dale-Chall Readability Formula

The Dale-Chall Readability Formula (Dale y Chall 1948) is one of the most respected and historically significant readability measures, known for its high correlation with reading comprehension scores. Its key innovation and distinguishing feature are its use of a list of words known to a certain percentage of 4th-grade students as a proxy for vocabulary difficulty, rather than relying on syllable or character counts. The classic Dale-Chall formula is:

$$\text{RawScore} = 0.1579 \cdot \text{PDW} + 0.0496 \cdot \text{ASL}.$$

PDW is the Percentage of Difficult Words (words not on the Dale-Chall Word List). ASL is the Average Sentence Length in words. If $\text{PDW} > 5\%$, then $\text{Adjusted Score} = \text{Raw Score} + 3.6365$. The metric is based on the Dale-Chall Word List. The original 1948 list contained 3,000 words, and the 1995 revision expanded it to approximately 3,000-word families (around 7,800 words). Any word not on this list is considered "difficult." Dale and Chall argued that existing formulas used unsatisfactory measures of word difficulty, such as word length or syllable count. They proposed that a word's familiarity, as measured by whether it was known by 4th-graders, was a superior metric. They validated their formula against comprehension tests and showed it had a higher correlation with comprehension than other leading formulas of the time (Dale y Chall 1948). A modern version of the formula was later proposed (Chall y Dale 1995). Chall and Dale updated the original 1948-word list to reflect changes in American English and children's vocabulary. They also simplified the calculation and provided clearer guidelines for its use. This work reaffirmed the formula's accuracy and utility for a modern audience. The core strength of the Dale-Chall formula is its grounding in vocabulary knowledge, which is a more direct measure of semantic difficulty than structural features such as syllable count. DuBay's review cites the Dale-Chall formula as one of the most reliable and valid measures available. He notes that in multiple validation studies, it has "consistently shown high correlations with reading comprehension", often higher than syllable-based formulas. DuBay attributes this property to its use of a word list, which directly measures a key component of reading comprehension: familiarity with vocabulary.

The primary advantages of Dale Chall metrics are their high correlation with actual reading comprehension tests, making it a trusted tool for educators and publishers, and its semantic focus. By focusing on word meaning (familiarity) rather than form (length), it more accurately captures why a text is difficult. Despite its high regard, the Dale-Chall formula has several well-documented limitations. The requirement to create a dedicated word list makes the process highly dependent on its cultural and temporal context.

The readability metrics have been adopted for dialogues of Pilot 2. Table 10 shows the results comparing the values obtained for the first and second speaker.

Other metrics are presented in [Deliverable 3.1](#) in the WP3 of Eloquence. In particular, in Section 5.3.2, the Automatic metrics and Domain-Specific metrics are described. Many automatic metrics need a ground truth to provide an assessment, and the Domain-Specific metrics typically adopt an LLM to evaluate the sentences. In the current case, we adopted word-based metrics since they provide a quick evaluation and carry out the response without a provided reference.

Table 10 Metrics from a set of dialogues of Pilot 2

File Name	FK1	FK2	CL1	CL2	GF1	GF2	Lin1	Lin2	DC1	DC2
dialog_20250619110225	12.78	16.54	10.9	15.9	14.74	18.56	13.83	18.41	12.8	13.84
dialog_20250709111611	14.53	13.8	12.68	15.2	17.56	17.03	17.15	13.23	11.7	12.87
dialog_20250619111823	13.42	14.32	13.34	16.91	16.43	15.39	14.19	12.55	13.12	14.06
dialog_20250709112548	10.8	15.69	10.23	16.48	14.22	17.64	12.42	16.79	12.08	13.33
dialog_20250708174657	11.5	12.77	11.36	16.12	15.34	13.54	12.79	8.81	10.38	12.83
dialog_20250619112816	14.15	13.47	11.81	13.2	17.8	15.39	17.74	14.46	12.93	13.87
dialog_20250708174316	12.63	15.61	11.97	15.55	16.01	17.87	13.88	16.88	12.15	12.82
dialog_20250717085527	13.06	14.34	11.95	16.87	16.12	15.45	14.81	13.09	13.26	13.37
dialog_20250708102144	13.87	16.56	11.15	16.13	16.5	19.67	16.09	18.55	12.82	13.4
dialog_20250709104934	12.38	13.35	10.81	14.34	15.28	16.86	14.9	14.81	11.81	12.94

Note: FK: Flesch-Kincaid, CL: Coleman Liau, GF: Gunning Fox, Lin: Linsear, DC: Dale-Chall.

From the Table 10, all the dialogues show a balanced score between the text 1 and the text 2. The text 1 corresponds to the set of sentences from the person that is asking information. Text 2 stands for the set of sentences replied by the system. The dialogues that are in bold are the ones that show the highest normalized difference that is still limited, showing a good dialogue performance in the pilot.

4.4.2 Pilot focused tagging of pilot dataset

The content read to the caller while waiting for an available human agent is selected based on the RAG retrieval results, determined by cosine similarity and subsequently re-scored using automatic evaluation metrics. Although this procedure was designed to correlate with human evaluation, it does not inherently provide any explanation to the end user.

To enhance the system’s explainability, we introduced an additional mechanism that informs users about the entities contributing to the generation of a particular response. For this purpose, we rely on the entity framework defined in [Deliverable 3.1](#). Specifically, we identify which entities are shared between the RAG input and the corresponding system-generated content.

The annotation scheme described in Deliverable 3.1 comprises 35 distinct entity types (e.g., AGE, CHILD_MEDICAL_HISTORY, SYMPTOM, TIME), developed collaboratively by domain experts and system developers. In our experiments, entities present in both the system inputs and generated outputs were manually verified.

Table presents the ratio of entities found in the generated content relative to the total number of entities in the corresponding input. These results are shown for the responses that achieved the highest human evaluation scores. The correlation between this ratio and the best human scores is 0.76, suggesting that entity overlap may serve as a promising indicator for improving the system’s explainability.

Table 11 UNS Pilot entity matching evaluation

	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	S7	S8	S9	S10
Human score	3.86	2.43	4.43	4.71	3.86	1.3	3.9	4.1	1.0	1.14
Entity matching	0.5	0.38	0.45	0.54	0.3	0.5	0.67	0.6	0.11	0.21

4.4.3 Masking data artificially for Pilot 4 (UNS)

Since, in the full system deployment, summaries (inputs) will be generated automatically, we also aimed to evaluate how the system behaves when certain information is omitted from the hand-crafted summaries. To perform this analysis, we again relied on **entity annotations**. We examined the available summaries and selected the entities most frequently occurring in the inputs:

- **AGE** – specifies the age of the child
- **BEHAVIOUR** – describes particular behaviour exhibited by the child
- **DEGREE** – indicates the severity of the symptoms

Not all entities appeared in every input, and some occurred multiple times within a single summary. When masking entities, the entire bullet point containing the selected entity was excluded from the input. After masking the selected entities, all generated snippets were re-scored using the same LLM-as-a-judge approach. In addition to the LLM scores, we introduced a new metric that counts the number of new snippets appearing among the top five ranked results compared to the original (unmasked) input. The results are summarised in Table 12. For the values missing in the table there was no given entity in summary.

Table 12 UNS Pilot masking evaluation.

	Summary	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	S7	S8	S9	S10
Entity	LLM best	3	3	3	4	4	2	5	4	1	1
AGE	Best	3	3		4	4	3	4	4		1
	New	1	1		1	1	1	2	0		1
BEHAVIOUR	Best	1	2	3		3		4		1	1
	New	1	4	0		1		1		2	1
DEGREE	Best	1		3	3	3		4		1	
	New	2		1	1	2		1		1	

From the presented data, it can be concluded that masking the AGE entity has the least impact on the output. The average number of newly ranked snippets is the lowest for this entity, and the best overall score changed only for a single input. In contrast, masking the BEHAVIOUR and DEGREE entities generally resulted in a decrease in the best score and an increase in the number of newly ranked snippets.

This behaviour can be explained by the fact that the age of the child often does not substantially affect the appropriateness of certain responses—for instance, the treatment of fever is typically the same regardless of age. On the other hand, excluding details related to specific behaviours or symptom severity can significantly reduce the relevance and adequacy of the generated answers.

4.5 Conclusion

A variety of methodologies have been developed and trialed for the purpose of offering explainable outputs as well as evaluating the level of explainability provided by LLM outputs. AMR graphs have been generated using dialogue-oriented datasets, as well as for QA domains – visually displaying key entities and relationships between the entities. Metrics have been applied to these AMR graphs for evaluating faithfulness, but find minor correlations, with no explainability metrics having been directly assessed. Similarly, the graph-based conversational modelling aids in the explainability of dialogue systems, displaying visually the manners in which a conversation can flow and where discrepancies from a ground-truth flow can occur. However, the metrics that can be derived from the deviation from a ground-truth flow are more closely aligned to faithfulness than to explainability. Readability metrics on the other hand, are computationally efficient and easily implemented, offering values to represent the level of legibility for an LLM response, which can be one facet of the explainability metric.

Evaluation comparing LLM and Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) approaches on the fused dataset found no strong correlations between the explainability metrics and the faithfulness metrics, providing confidence that they measure distinct properties. Additionally, these LLM-based explainability metrics demonstrate greater consistency when compared to the LLM-based faithfulness metrics, exhibiting significantly lower standard deviations and having means that were closer to the maximum possible values.

An entity matching evaluation conducted on Pilot 4 found that the ratio of shared entities between the RAG input and the generated content correlated with the best human evaluation scores at 0.76, indicating that entity overlap is a promising indicator for system explainability. When artificially masking data in Pilot 4 to test robustness, masking the AGE entity had the least impact on the output quality, while masking the BEHAVIOUR and DEGREE entities generally resulted in a decrease in the best scores and a significant reduction in the relevance of the generated answers. In Pilot 2, the application of readability metrics (such as Flesch-Kincaid, Coleman-Liau, Gunning Fox, Linsear, and Dale-Chall) revealed a balanced score between the complexity levels of the user's sentences (Text 1) and the system's responses (Text 2).

5 Security/privacy evaluation

5.1 Introduction

Federated learning has emerged as a transformative paradigm for training LLMs in a decentralized manner, enabling organizations to harness the collective power of distributed data sources while maintaining data governance and privacy constraints. However, this approach introduces novel security and privacy challenges that must be carefully addressed. Unlike centralized learning systems where data resides in a single location, federated architectures distribute the training process across multiple clients or organizations, each retaining local data ownership while contributing to a global model through iterative parameter updates.

The federation of LLMs presents a unique attack surface, combining the vulnerabilities inherent to distributed systems with the specific risks associated with deep learning models. Participants in a federated system must balance the benefits of collaborative model improvement against potential data leakage, model poisoning, and inference attacks. This section provides comprehensive research of the security and privacy dimensions of federated LLM systems, drawing from real-world implementations and pilot deployments.

LLMs may unintentionally expose sensitive information through multiple types of vulnerabilities (Schulhoff, et al. 2024, Yi, et al. 2024). One prominent risk is prompt leakage, where adversaries craft inputs to uncover system prompts, hidden instructions, or internal behaviours of the model, often by subtly circumventing safety mechanisms rather than issuing overtly malicious commands. For instance, instead of directly stating “ignore previous instructions,” an attacker might request a description of the model’s internal debugging or reasoning process, thereby inducing the model to reveal aspects of its configuration or control logic.

Another closely related threat is training data reconstruction (Kanth Nakka, et al. 2025), in which an attacker exploits the model’s memorization of its training corpus to retrieve information about specific individuals or records. Rather than soliciting generic completions, the adversary can embed detailed cues about a target in the prompt (e.g., name and birth year) to increase the likelihood that the model reproduces sensitive attributes seen during training, such as medical or personal details that are irrelevant to the current query (Selvam and Ghosh 2025). These behaviours illustrate how LLMs can retain and potentially disclose private information from their training data, effectively bypassing safeguards intended to prevent such leakage.

5.2 Assessing data privacy in Federated Learning

A key privacy challenge with federated learning is the risk of data leaking between the clients’ contributing data. In ELOQUENCE’s Pilot 1, we are aiming to create a helpful global assistant, e.g. that provides reminders about appointments or medical treatments, based on information from past conversations occurred in the domestic environment. To do this, Pilot 1 trains a language model using data from several sources (simulated domestic environments) and makes it available for everyone to use, essentially, a common language model-based assistant. However, there is a risk that someone, e.g. users from a different household, could potentially uncover Private Identifiable Information (PII), like names, addresses, or sensitive medical details, from this global model. Simply knowing a person’s address is an unacceptable privacy concern. This risk grows if someone can connect that address to other information, for example, discovering that “[Person’s Name] received chemotherapy at [Hospital Name] in January 2025”.

While clients do not directly share raw data, several leakage vectors exist:

- **Model Inversion Attacks:** An attacker with access to model weights may attempt to invert the model to reconstruct training data. For LLMs, this is particularly concerning as language models trained on sensitive text may memorize and reproduce exact training samples. In LLMs, model inversion attacks analyse model outputs, gradients, and/or parameters to infer sensitive details about their training data (Song y Namiot 2022).
- **Membership Inference Attacks:** Attackers may determine whether a specific data sample was used in training by querying the model and analysing its confidence scores or outputs (Carlini, et al. 2021). In federated settings, an adversarial client could potentially infer membership of other clients’ data.

- Gradient Leakage: Even without access to full models, gradient updates can leak training data through gradient inversion attacks. Recent research (Fernandez-de-Retana, y otros 2025) has shown that individual gradients computed during federated training can be inverted to recover reasonable approximations of the original training data.

For mitigating these risks and prevent LLMs from simply memorizing sensitive information, two main approaches are reported in literature: (1) carefully curating the training data and (2) incorporating specific techniques, like differential training (DP), into the LLM training process. The former uses PII scrubbing, which involves removing PII from the training text or audio, often automatically handled by Named Entity Recognition (NER) algorithms to flag what needs to be removed and are language dependent. On the contrary, DP is not about removing data, but to make the training process robust to individual data points, providing a formal guarantee that the model's behaviour is not overly reliant on any one person's data and being language agnostic. DP works by modifying the gradients used to update the model's parameters, e.g. by adding noise (Xianzhi Li 2024) or clipping them, also known as Differentially Private Stochastic Gradient Descent (DP-SGD). The latter is the proposed approach for privacy-preserving training in ELOQUENCE.

5.2.1 Perplexity

Perplexity (Jelinek, et al. 1977) is commonly used to measure how well a LLM performs on unseen data (Vaswani, et al. 2017), that is, its utility. While the theoretically "perfect" minimization of the training loss would correspond to the model memorizing each training example, this goes against the generalization purpose of language modelling. In fact, only a subset of the training data is memorized, and achieving some level of memorization may even be necessary for optimal model performance. The effectiveness or utility of a language model θ is therefore assessed by calculating its perplexity on a test set of tokens w_1, \dots, w_n that the model has not seen before:

$$\text{PPL}(w_1, \dots, w_n; \theta) = \exp\left(-\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \log \Pr(w_i \mid w_1, \dots, w_{i-1}; \theta)\right),$$

Computed over the summation of log-conditional probabilities $\Pr(w_i \mid w_1, \dots, w_{i-1}; \theta)$ per each token in the sequence. A lower perplexity value indicates better model performance on unseen data. Perplexity can be computed as a standard measure of model utility, shown when evaluating trade-off between privacy (as per below metric) and language modelling capability.

5.2.2 Differential Privacy

Differential Privacy (DP) of a mechanism $\mathcal{M}: X \rightarrow Y$ is (ϵ, δ) differentially private if for any pair of adjacent datasets D and D' and measurable set of outputs $\mathcal{O} \subseteq Y$, the following holds:

$$\Pr(\mathcal{M}(D) \in \mathcal{O}) \leq e^\epsilon \Pr(\mathcal{M}(D') \in \mathcal{O}) + \delta,$$

where $\epsilon > 0, \delta \in [0,1]$. This definition expresses that the presence or absence of a single data record in the dataset has only a small, controlled effect on the probability distribution of the mechanism's outputs. ϵ is also known as the privacy budget, lower meaning stronger privacy.

5.2.3 Multilingual Privacy

Multilingual Attacks exploit the multilingual nature of LLMs to infer properties of training data from one language based on model behaviour in another language. For example, an adversary might query the model extensively in a high-resource language to infer information about training data in a low-resource language; cross-lingual transfer learning mechanisms built into multilingual models can inadvertently transfer information about sensitive data from one language community to another. In academic literature there is a gap on explicit multilingual attack studies in FL-LLM, but current multilingual FL works plus FL-LLM attack benchmarks can be used as proxies (Joe-Wong, et al. 2025).

Federated LLM systems, particularly those trained on multilingual data, face specialized attack vectors related to language diversity and cross-linguistic information leakage. We should consider some privacy-preserving mechanisms designed not only for one language but accounting for information leakage through cross-lingual embeddings thus Federated Defence Strategies should be placed to counter for such attacks:

- Apply language-specific differential privacy bounds to ensure consistency across languages
- Isolate language-specific model components during aggregation
- Implement strict data governance ensuring that federated training only occurs with properly anonymized multilingual data.

Protecting the privacy of the user's data used to federated train language models, whether through removing personally identifiable information (PII scrubbing) or using techniques like DP (Charles, Ganesh, et al. 2024), comes at a cost. There is a trade-off between privacy and model performance: *stronger privacy measures can sometimes reduce how well the model performs*. While PII scrubbing removes many pieces of personal information, it is not foolproof and requires carefully balancing privacy with the usefulness of the data. DP training significantly reduces the risk of leakage, but it is not perfect, especially when dealing with duplicated or commonly occurring personal information (Kanth Nakka, et al. 2025, Lukas, et al. 2023).

Based on previous research, we plan to measure PII extraction rates in federated multilingual LLMs, where threat model focuses on attackers attempting to recover sensitive information from responses via black-box probing, membership inference, or reconstruction-style queries against the federated LLM. Details on the architecture and results will be reported in upcoming deliverables.

5.3 Conclusion

The federation of large language models introduces significant security and privacy challenges that extend beyond traditional centralized learning systems. Successful deployment of federated LLMs requires a comprehensive approach addressing data confidentiality, secure weight management, protection against gradient leakage, and defences against structured attacks exploiting model characteristics such as multilingualism.

Organizations implementing federated LLM systems must employ multiple layers of privacy protection, including differential privacy, secure aggregation, robust aggregation methods, and careful governance of data usage policies. As federated LLM technology matures, privacy and security considerations must remain central to system design rather than treated as an afterthought. The field continues to evolve with new attack vectors being discovered and novel defences being developed. Organizations deploying federated LLMs should maintain awareness of emerging research in privacy attacks and defences, regularly update their security protocols, and conduct ongoing privacy impact assessments.

Current work that has been conducted within this domain uncovered a significant data leakage risk in Pilot 1, a global assistant trained using federated learning, where external users could potentially uncover Private Identifiable Information (PII) or sensitive medical details from the resulting global model. To mitigate privacy risks, Differentially Private Stochastic Gradient Descent (DP-SGD) is established as the proposed approach for privacy-preserving training within ELOQUENCE, offering a formal and language agnostic guarantee compared to the alternative method of PII scrubbing. Specific federated defence strategies are defined to counter specialized multilingual

attacks, which include applying language-specific differential privacy bounds and ensuring the isolation of language-specific model components during aggregation.

6 Bias evaluation

6.1 Introduction

LLMs and Automatic Speech Recognition systems have achieved remarkable performance across diverse natural language processing tasks, yet their widespread deployment increasingly reveals a critical challenge: the manifestation of inherent social biases that can perpetuate and amplify harmful stereotypes (Gallegos 2024). These biases emerge from multiple sources including unrepresentative training data, algorithmic artifacts in the in-context learning paradigm, and internal model mechanisms that systematically skew predictions toward particular groups (H. F. Zhou 2024). As those systems become integrated into high-stakes applications spanning healthcare, employment, and financial services, rigorous bias evaluation frameworks have become essential to ensure fairness and mitigate potential discriminatory harms.

Recent research has established comprehensive taxonomies for bias evaluation across multiple model levels—from learned embeddings and token probabilities to generated text outputs. Contemporary evaluation methodologies employ task-agnostic approaches such as the B-score metric, which detects bias through comparative analysis of single-turn versus multi-turn response distributions without requiring external annotations or ground-truth assumptions (Vo 2025). However, existing benchmarks frequently underestimate inherent model vulnerabilities; the FLEX benchmark demonstrates that LLMs generate biased responses even under simple adversarial prompts when traditional fairness evaluations suggest satisfactory performance (Jung 2025). Standardization remains limited despite recent IEEE frameworks establishing algorithmic bias considerations across the AI system lifecycle (IEEE 2024), highlighting the necessity for more rigorous evaluation standards.

The upcoming sections of this document detail various definitions of biases in this context that are useful for upcoming developments in ELOQUENCE.

6.2 Cultural bias metrics

The detection and quantification of “cultural biases” in LLMs and ASRs has been approached from a variety of stand points in the state of the art. Recent research recognizes that linguistic and cultural nuances embedded in large-scale training data may introduce systematic disparities in how AI models process, generate, and interpret content across different populations (Navigli 2023). Methodologies for investigating these biases commonly span both data-centric and model-centric perspectives, targeting not only overt disparities in representation or outcomes but also subtle, context-dependent manifestations.

Data distribution analyses are frequently employed to identify imbalances in the representation of cultural, regional, and demographic groups within the underlying datasets, as these disparities tend to propagate into model behaviour. Evaluation methods have thus evolved to incorporate both quantitative and qualitative strategies—ranging from counterfactual fairness testing, contextual and sentiment analysis, to stereotype and ideology detection in model outputs—to systematically surface and interpret biased associations, especially those not directly encoded but rather emerging through model generalization.

The upcoming text provides a taxonomy of state-of-the-art perspectives for “cultural bias” and their corresponding references.

- **Moral values alignment:** Evaluates the extent to which LLMs’ ethical reasoning and moral judgments align with human moral principles across different cultural contexts. This approach recognizes that moral values are not universal but are fundamentally influenced by language, culture, and geographic region (K. C. Zhou 2025).
- **Regional knowledge representation:** Regional knowledge representation assesses how LLMs encode, retrieve, and manifest culturally specific knowledge across different geographic regions and whether models exhibit adequate diversity and fairness in representing global cultures (S. V. Singh 2024).
- **Ideology Alignment:** Examines the susceptibility of LLMs to absorb, reflect, and generalize ideological biases across political topics and the extent to which models exhibit systematic political leanings in their outputs (S. R.-S. Singh 2024).

- **Adherence to Universal Human Rights:** Evaluates whether AI systems, including both LLMs and ASRs, pose risks to internationally recognized human rights such as non-discrimination, equality, access to information, freedom of thought, privacy, health, and security. This approach translates the UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights into context-aware computational methodologies consisting of three components: identifying evaluation tasks relevant to specific deployment contexts that impact rights, designing metrics to measure the scope, scale, and likelihood of potential rights violations, and interpreting outcomes through a rights-based lens that centers real-world harms.

However, our analysis of the state-of-the-art reveals how cultural biases is rarely approached through several metrics, but more often as an alignment to a set of principles or core values gathered as responses to a well-crafted questionnaire. Based on this insight, we plan to create a multidimensional assessment of cultural bias by crafting an evaluation questionnaire that is composed by the four dimensions listed above. Details on the architecture and results will be reported in upcoming deliverables.

6.3 Gender bias metrics

To quantify gender biases in a particular context, it is important to first establish a clear definition of what a bias-free system would look like. This requires a thoughtful reflection on the desired behaviour of the analysed model and the impact that potential biases might have.

We propose to approach this task from two different perspectives, what we name *Stereotyping Bias* (\mathcal{S}_b) and *Representation Bias* (\mathcal{R}_b). The former quantifies how a given LLM is far from gender neutrality given a domain. The latter considers the LLM bias with respect to what is observed in society. In the upcoming text, we provide an overview on how we propose measure both perspectives of gender bias given a specific context.

- **Stereotyping bias:** (\mathcal{S}_b) quantifies the extent to which a model is far away from gender neutrality within a context and given by a specific language (\mathcal{L}) and a LLM model (\mathcal{M}). To do so, it quantifies the disparities in average association score across genders for each of the economic sectors: primary, secondary and tertiary.

To calculate the overall \mathcal{S}_b across sectors we first calculate the stereotyping bias for a specific sector s as the inner disparity $\mathcal{J}\mathcal{D}_s(\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{M})$ by first computing the model's average difference between association scores as between females and males. This difference is calculated for each i -th sentence generated for females $a_s(f_i)$ and males $a_s(m_i)$ between the total number n of male and female oriented sentences generated for \mathcal{L} and s .

$$\mathcal{J}\mathcal{D}_s(\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{M}) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=0}^n (a_s(f_i) - a_s(m_i))$$

The overall stereotyping bias \mathcal{S}_b across sectors for \mathcal{M} and \mathcal{L} is computed as the average inner disparity across all three economic sectors:

$$\mathcal{S}_b(\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{M}) = \frac{1}{3} \sum_{s=1}^3 \mathcal{J}\mathcal{D}_s(\mathcal{M}, \mathcal{L})$$

A model \mathcal{M} trained for language \mathcal{L} without stereotyping bias $\mathcal{S}_b(\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{M}) = 0$, would produce equal average association scores for male and female targets in economic sectors. Negative values indicate bias favouring males, while positive values indicate bias favouring females. Stereotyping bias is specific to each model and the language in which it was trained.

- **Representation bias:** With a broader view and given a domain, *representation bias* (\mathcal{R}_b) generally refers to the underrepresentation or overrepresentation of certain groups (such as genders or ethnicities) as compared to their prevalence in the overall target population. However, in the context of our research, we adopt a definition of *representation bias*, particularly tailored to the context of our analysis. Here, \mathcal{R}_b is

understood as the divergence of a model’s internal representation of genders from the actual societal gender distributions in the workforce.

We define the overall representation bias across economic sectors for a given LLM \mathcal{M} trained for language \mathcal{L} as:

$$\mathcal{R}_g(\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{M}) = \frac{1}{3} \sum_{s=1}^3 (JD_s(\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{M}) - OD_s(\mathcal{L}))$$

Here, $JD_s(\mathcal{M}, \mathcal{L})$ is the model’s inner disparity score as defined above, and $OD_s(\mathcal{L})$ represents the observed gender ratio in economic sector s in the country associated with the language \mathcal{L} . $OD_s(\mathcal{L})$ is calculated by comparing the percentages of females and males in sector s using data from the Global Gender Gap Index (WeForum n.d.) across different countries.

A balanced model ($\mathcal{R}_g = 0$) perfectly reproduces societal gender distributions. Negative values indicate a model preference for males compared to the real prevalence, while positive values indicate a preference for females. This metric helps language modelers ensure accurate societal representations in their models.

6.4 Multimodal bias

6.4.1 Device-Induced bias in ASR

In the context of on-device inference with ASR, one of the primary challenges in software-centric industrial setups is managing device heterogeneity. This issue arises because different manufacturers and hardware variations can influence detection processes. As illustrated in Figure , varying devices can produce distinct digital representations from the same acoustic information, thereby affecting the entire detection pipeline, including pre-processing, feature extraction, the Wake-up-Word (WuW) model detector, and any score manipulation procedures.

Figure 5 Block diagram of inference pipeline of WuW classification within a multi-device scenario.

Note: Diverse devices produce different digital information stemming from microphone transfer functions and digital signal processing, consequently affecting the whole inference pipeline. Starting with the pre-processing, then the feature extraction, the WuW model, and finally the post-processing.

In order to quantify this specific type of bias, we use three distinct metrics:

- **Balanced accuracy:** Balanced accuracy (BA) is a metric used to fairly evaluate classification performance across unbalanced datasets. In this setting, we calculate BA as the average accuracy across devices (d):

$$BA = \frac{1}{b-a} \sum_{d=a}^{d=b} acc(d)$$

- **F1-score of the positive class:** The F1-score is the harmonic mean of precision and recall and is used as an evaluation metric, particularly when the class distribution is imbalanced: $F1 - score = 2 \times \frac{Precision \times Recall}{Precision + Recall}$

Being: $Precision = \frac{TP}{TP+FP}$ and, $Recall = \frac{TP}{TP+FN}$ where TP is true positive, FP is false positive, and FN is false negative. The F1-score balances the model's ability to identify relevant instances (recall) and its accuracy in doing so (precision).

- **Wassertein-distance for output distributions:** To ensure robustness across devices, we quantify the discrepancy between probability distributions using the first-order Wasserstein distance. Let μ and ν be two probability distributions over the speech feature space $\mathcal{X} \subset \mathbb{R}^d$, corresponding to audio captured from two different devices. The Wasserstein1 distance (also known as Earth Mover's Distance) between μ and ν is defined as:

$$W_1(\mu, \nu) = \inf_{\gamma \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)} \int_{\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{X}} \|x - y\| d\gamma(x, y)$$

where $\Pi(\mu, \nu)$ is the set of all couplings (joint distributions) γ with marginals μ and ν . Intuitively, $W_1(\mu, \nu)$ measures the minimal "effort" required to transform one distribution into the other, given a ground cost $\|x - y\|$.

In this context, minimizing W_1 encourages invariance to device-specific transformations and aligns the probability distributions across devices, improving generalization and robustness in WuW.

6.4.2 Bias in Multiple-choice Question and Answer

Understanding spoken language is essential for creating natural and intuitive interactions between humans and machines. Advances in large audio language models (LALMs) are making it possible to properly interpret audio context. Recently, numerous large audio language models (LALMs) have appeared, including LTU (Gong, et al. 2024), SALMONN (Sun, et al. 2024), GAMA (Ghosh, Kumar, et al. 2024), Audio Flamingo 2 (Ghosh, Kong, et al. 2025), Qwen2.5-Omni (Xu, et al. 2025), Audio Reasoner (Xie, et al. 2025), Kimi-Audio (Ding, et al. 2025), and Audio Flamingo 3 (Goel, et al. 2025), directly linked to the rapid progress being made in multimodal large language models (MLLMs). These models are usually evaluated in multiple-choice question answering (MCQA) tasks, through benchmarks that incorporate reasoning abilities, such as MMAU (Sakshi, et al. 2024), MMAR (Ma, et al. 2025), SAKURA (Yang, et al. n.d.) and MMSU (Wang, et al. n.d.).

When evaluating bias in multiple-choice tests, an answer is marked as potentially biased if it is chosen significantly more often than other answers that are equally valid. However, consistently selecting the single correct answer is not considered a sign of bias. Robustness and bias of LALMs and LLMs, and specifically in multiple-choice question answering (MCQA) tasks, have been reported to be highly sensitive to several factors present in the evaluation benchmarks as the choice ordering (Zheng, et al. 2024), answer phrasing, and distractor wording (Balepur, Rudinger y Lee Boyd-Graber 2025), which can cause significant accuracy fluctuation in the LALM responses. To account for these possible fluctuations in LLM and LALM, we propose to systematically introduce multiple textual perturbations to augment current MQCA benchmarks:

- **Choice Ordering:** All or several possible permutations of multi-choices can be evaluated, thus revealing substantial performance swings depending on where the correct answer is placed.
- **Question, Answer, and Distractor Rephrasing:** Using generative models to translate original prompts by paraphrased versions for each element.
- **Mix of Perturbations:** Modifications are randomly mixed, reflecting real-world variability and producing diverse evaluation scenarios.

Figure 6 illustrates the evaluation protocol designed to assess the models' performance across four perturbations applied to the original benchmark. This approach aims to mitigate potential biases introduced by the benchmark's construction and gain insights to advice in future evaluation design. The correct answer for each example is highlighted in green.

Figure 6 Evaluation protocol example for each perturbation applied to a benchmark in isolation.

6.4.2.1 Metrics

We propose evaluating model's performance using the following metrics:

- Accuracy, which is usually reported through mean, standard deviation, minimum, and maximum values.
- Consistency rate (CR), similar as described in (Nalbandyan, Shahbazyan and Evelina 2025)
- Correctness Rate (CoR), to gauge the reliability and correctness of the results.

CoR and CR capture complementary aspects of the model behaviour. Let $Q = Q_1, Q_2, \dots, Q_n$ denote the set of questions, where n represents the total number of triplet benchmarks (question, audio, and choices). Correspondingly, $R = \{R_1, R_2, \dots, R_n\}$ represents the collection of response sets, with each $R_i = \{r_{i1}, r_{i2}, \dots, r_{im}\}$ indicating responses for individual questions, where m is the number of different perturbations evaluated. $G_i = \{g_{i1}, g_{i2}, \dots, g_n\}$ represents the list of ground truth answers.

Consistency rate (CR) is defined as:

$$CR = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m \sum_{k=j+1}^m \frac{\delta(r_{ij}, r_{ik})}{\binom{m}{2}}$$

where $\delta(x, y)$ is the Kronecker delta,

$$\delta(x, y) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x = y \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

CR assesses internal robustness by examining the agreement among multiple responses. CR is applicable when ground-truth answers or distractors remain unchanged.

Correctness rate (CoR) is defined as:

$$CoR = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{m} \sum_{j=1}^m \text{correctness}(r_{ij}, g_i),$$

where the accuracy of each response (r, g) is determined by a benchmark that provides a correctness score: 1 for a correct answer and 0 for an incorrect one. The CoR metric evaluates external validity by comparing each response to the ground truth, regardless of the order of elements. This evaluation is applicable to any change we introduce through our methods. Note that MMAU (Sakshi, et al. 2024), MMAR (Ma, et al. 2025), SAKURA (Yang, et

al. n.d.) and MMSU (Wang, et al. n.d.) benchmarks use different methods to assess correctness, ranging from regular expression matching to requiring an exact content match.

6.4.2.2 Preliminary results

In Table 13, we present the performance metrics for the four LALMs, using the default setup that preserves the original order of answer choices, question phrasing, ground truth answers, and distractors. Our results are consistent with previous studies, showing a slight accuracy difference of approximately $\pm 2\%$. This small variation may be due to differences in decoding strategies or library versions. The Table 13 also includes results obtained through random choice selection. Notably, in the MMAR benchmark, random selection achieved an accuracy of 17.1% on questions with only two options.

Table 13 Accuracy (%) with the default benchmark setup across three benchmarks

Model	MMAU				MMAR				MMSU		
	Sound	Music	Speech	Avg	Sound	Music	Speech	Avg	Perception	Reasoning	Avg
Random choice	28.5	23.7	24.9	25.7	34.6	26.2	36.7	33.0	26.4	25.0	25.4
Audio Flamingo 2	70.6	72.5	45.1	62.7	47.3	43.7	45.9	45.3	32.6	51.5	41.8
Audio Flamingo 3	80.2	74.0	65.8	73.3	53.3	49.5	62.6	58.5	46.4	76.6	61.0
Qwen2.5-Omni-7B	71.8	67.1	65.8	68.2	60.6	42.2	62.6	59.0	47.6	78.1	62.4
Kimi-Audio-7B-Instruct	76.3	67.1	70.0	71.1	52.1	43.2	58.5	54.0	46.1	71.5	58.4

Table 14 summarizes models averaged performance across tasks in the three benchmarks studied, and under choice permutation. The results demonstrate a moderate level of variability across LALMs, indicating a degree of robustness to input perturbations. However, performance on the MMAU benchmark revealed a significant divergence in results based on order permutation of choices. Specifically, in MMAU some models exhibited a high variance, with standard deviations reaching up to 2.7 points and, in extreme cases, accuracy deviating by as much as 8.3 points from the mean accuracy.

Table 14 Effect of choices permutation across benchmarks

Model	MMAU			MMAR			MMSU		
	ACC% (mean \pm std, [min, max])	CR	CoR	ACC% (mean \pm std, [min, max])	CR	CoR	ACC% (mean \pm std, [min, max])	CR	CoR
Audio Flamingo 2	58.9 \pm 1.4 [57.3, 63.0]	0.80	0.43	44.9 \pm 0.8 [43.0, 45.9]	0.74	0.21	41.2 \pm 1.2 [38.2, 42.8]	0.63	0.15
Audio Flamingo 3	72.8 \pm 0.6 [71.4, 74.0]	0.88	0.63	58.0 \pm 0.8 [56.9, 60.1]	0.84	0.40	60.8 \pm 0.4 [60.2, 61.4]	0.76	0.42
Qwen2.5-Omni-7B	68.1 \pm 1.4 [65.3, 70.6]	0.76	0.49	57.4 \pm 0.9 [55.7, 58.8]	0.74	0.36	62.5 \pm 0.3 [62.0, 63.4]	0.63	0.40
Kimi-Audio-7B-it	63.8 \pm 2.7 [58.9, 71.1]	0.69	0.33	54.5 \pm 0.9 [53.2, 56.7]	0.65	0.25	58.5 \pm 0.6 [57.5, 59.8]	0.64	0.27

6.4.3 Bias in Federated Learning

Federated Learning (FL) introduces novel fairness challenges due to decentralized training and data heterogeneity across clients. Two complementary perspectives define fairness in FL:

- Group fairness** ensures equitable treatment across demographic groups within the global model. The central challenge arises from non-IID data distributions: when clients possess heterogeneous sensitive attribute distributions, local debiasing fails to guarantee global group fairness. Recent evidence reveals bias propagation, wherein participation from biased clients actively deteriorates group fairness through parameter aggregation. We evaluate group fairness for the task of text-summarization and instruction tuning using the following metrics:

- a. **ROUGE-L standard deviation across languages:** ROUGE-L (Lin 2004) is a metric used to evaluate automatic text summarization and machine translation systems by measuring the Longest Common Subsequence (LCS) between a generated summary and a human-written reference summary. Unlike n-gram overlap metrics, ROUGE-L captures similarity by identifying the longest sequence of words that appears in both texts, even if they are not consecutive, which helps evaluate how well the summary maintains the original structure and flow. We quantify the standard deviation of ROUGE-L across training languages as a method to quantify the group fairness in text-summarization.
 - b. **BERTScore standard deviation across languages:** BERTScore (Zhang 2019) leverages the pre-trained contextual embeddings from BERT and matches words in candidate and reference sentences by cosine similarity. It has been shown to correlate with human judgment on sentence-level and system-level evaluation. Moreover, BERTScore computes precision, recall, and F1 measure, which can be useful for evaluating different language generation tasks.
- **Client fairness:** focuses on equitable treatment of participating devices, ensuring clients contributing diverse or high-quality data experience proportionally better performance. This perspective addresses contribution evaluation, fair incentive distribution, and client selection in decentralized ecosystems.
 - a. **Average client utility** measures the overall mean utility (e.g., model accuracy, reward, or benefit) achieved across all clients, providing a general indicator of fairness at the population level.
 - b. **Average client utility dispersion** quantifies the variability or inequality in client utilities, typically assessed through variance, standard deviation, or fairness indices, to capture how evenly performance is distributed among clients.
 - c. **Min-max utility** evaluates fairness by comparing the minimum and maximum achieved utilities across clients, reflecting the gap between the least and most advantaged participants and guiding mechanisms to reduce extreme disparities.

These two dimensions reveal fundamental tensions: optimizing for group fairness may introduce performance disparities across clients, while prioritizing client fairness without group constraints can propagate demographic biases into the global model. Contemporary research emphasizes developing comprehensive frameworks addressing both perspectives while maintaining privacy and computational efficiency.

6.5 Conclusion

In summary, while recent advances have deepened our understanding of bias evaluation in language and speech models, the current landscape remains fragmented and often insufficiently aligned with real-world deployment needs. Addressing these gaps calls for integrated frameworks that extend beyond isolated metrics toward holistic fairness assessment across modalities, tasks, and deployment contexts.

Building on these insights, upcoming project deliverables will introduce operational definitions of bias tailored to ELOQUENCE, establishing a foundation for systematic benchmarking, mitigation strategies, and trustworthy AI development practices.

7 Fused metrics for evaluation

7.1 Introduction

With the desire to produce ELOQUENCE “eMetrics”, we aim to consolidate important metrics within a composite metric. These important metrics are explainability and faithfulness. Both of which will be produced from several relevant metrics, to cover a wide range of utility.

7.2 Faithfulness fusion – ELOQUENCE fused dataset

In the aims of improving correlation with human judgement, we also conduct experimentation on the fusion of the various metrics. Each metric can capture different features between the ground truth and generated texts, based on how they operate - such as n-gram approaches focusing on the lexical structure of the text, whilst LLMs offer a more abstractive metric with higher-level reasoning capabilities. The Explainable Boosting Machine⁷ (EBM) algorithm has been selected to weight the metrics in the aims of maximising similarity with the human judgement. This algorithm operates in a more explainable way than other algorithms such as Random Forest (RF), with the feature importances calculated able to be used directly with the scores outputted to compute the output variable - which in our case is a faithfulness metric. This weighted metric is then tested on a blind subset of the relevant domains. The weightings identified through application of the EBM algorithm are displayed in Table 15.

Table 16 details and compares the correlations with human judgement that each metric attains, as well as the fused metric which incorporates an assortment of the metrics in aim of improving correlation.

Table 15 Explainable Boosting Machine faithfulness metric fusion

Metric	Short-Form QA	Long-Form QA	Conversational QA	Summarisation
LLM	0.188	0.151	0.222	0.312
N-gram	0.287	0.188	0.257	0.128
Embedding	0.057	0.091	0.073	
Graph	0.187	0.381	0.302	0.560
Matching	0.152	0.189	0.146	

Table 16 Fused faithfulness metric evaluation against human judgement

Metric	Short-Form QA	Long-Form QA	Conversational QA	Summarisation
Prev. Best	0.815***	0.659***	0.461***	0.578***
Fused Metric	0.820***	0.795***	0.507***	0.581***

Note: Correlations with $P \leq 0.05$, $P \leq 0.01$ and $P < 0.001$ are marked *, ** and *** respectively.

The weightings of the fused metric have been provided in Table 15, detailing the importance of each metric in the optimisation of human correlation, as identified through the EBM network. Considering the weak correlations displayed by graph-based metrics, they are consistently deemed highly important for the fused metric, except for short-form QA. Reasons for this are likely due to the comparative simplicity within short-form evaluation, with graphs likely being superfluous for evaluation. However, within the summarisation domain (which contains the highest level of ambiguity and the longest form text) it is shown that graph-based metrics are exceedingly important, which is unsurprising considering that it is the domain that pioneered this approach. Furthermore, this importance is likely increased due to the matching metrics not being relevant, with no matches (neither exact nor lexical) being made, as well as BERTScore being identified as not important to the aligning with faithfulness. Codebase of metric implementation as part of Milestone 1.2 is provided at <https://huggingface.co/datasets/Brunel-AI/ELOQUENCE>. This codebase covers the production of faithfulness metrics across: ROUGE, BERTScore, LLM-as-a-

⁷ <https://interpret.ml/docs/ebm.html>

judge, exact match, lexical match and graph-based metrics. The generation of graphs to be stored as text within the dataset using Penman notation. The implementation of the EBM algorithm for the production of weights for a specific task (identifying the feature importance of each metric), as well as the loading of EBM weights for the production of a weighted metric that is more highly correlated with human judgement. Finally, this codebase is developed for native support of the fused dataset, featuring pre-loaded prompts that have been used for our evaluative testing, yet the codebase also supports custom prompting and support for additional datasets through user inputted schema arguments.

Table 16 details and compares the correlations with human judgement that each metric attains, as well as the fused metric which incorporates an assortment of the metrics in aim of improving correlation. For these correlations, we have opted to correlate for the human Likert judgement, for the sake of brevity. Additionally, it is worth noting that the correlations achieved for the fused metric is gathered using a blind test set, to ensure that the test is fair.

Through application of the EBM algorithm for identifying the level of importance that each metric has, we can observe that LLM-based metrics and n-gram based metrics provide the most utility for a fused metric. For long-form QA, the graph-based metrics contribute to 38.1% of the fused metric's outputted value, with the LLM-based techniques adding an additional 15.1% combined. Whilst for short-form QA, n-gram metrics contributes 28.7% and the LLM-based approaches contribute an additional 18.8%. These metrics both use pre-trained transformers to compute their judgements, albeit in different ways, compared to the other metrics which are comparatively simpler.

7.3 Explainability fusion – ELOQUENCE fused dataset

For RAG-based evaluation we identify and define three components of explainability:

1. Confidence – A value to represent the relevance of the retrieved document
2. Explanation – A value to represent the explainability of an LLM response, which is produced through an LLM-derived natural language output
3. Readability – A value to represent the quality of the written response in a grammatical and legibility manner.

The incorporation of the Confidence and Explanation components will represent the overall explainability of the LLM. For non-RAG systems, the Confidence component cannot be utilized, as there is no external document store with which to compute the relevance of a retrieved document. A readability score is excluded from compilation into the fused metric due to the subjective manner with which readability can be linked to explainability. The desired readability level is highly dependent upon the reading level of the user, and thus the level of explainability offered by an LLM response would change depending on the user. For example, a user with a comparatively low reading level may not deem a response as well-explained if the vocabulary used is above their reading level.

The fusion of the explainability metrics functions differently to how the faithfulness metrics have been fused, this is because the explainability metrics are not attempting to simulate a human's judgement. Instead, they aim to provide the user with the rationale behind a decision, with the final metric produced merely reflecting this rationale and aiding in the ongoing evaluation of our models. Due to this difference in objective, we do not use the EBM algorithm, instead the explainability components are equally weighted to produce a final value.

7.4 eMetric Fusion

Through the range of domains that have been assessed, and the metric importances that have been identified in each domain, we observe the need for eMetrics to be both task-specific and for there to be the option for them to be user-defined. Thus, the weighting between faithfulness and explainability, as well as the additional components to be incorporated as part of later milestones, should be flexible. However, whilst only faithfulness and explainability metrics comprise the eMetrics, the default configuration will be for the weightings to be equal.

7.5 Conclusion

The fusion of metrics to produce the eMetric is to be domain-dependent, with specific domains requiring alternative weightings between metrics. However, the user should also be able to define this weighting, dependent on their desired use case as well. The faithfulness score comprises metrics across the following categories: LLM-as-a-judge, AMR graphs, n-grams, BERTScore and lexical matching. The weightings between these metrics used to compute the faithfulness score is domain-dependent and provided in Table 15. The codebase for the production of these metrics is found along with the fused dataset at: <https://huggingface.co/datasets/Brunel-AI/ELOQUENCE> . Whereas the explainability metrics are to be weighted equally, across retrieved document similarity score (for RAG applications) and the LLM-derived explainability score. Due to only faithfulness and explainability metrics currently being featured within the eMetrics, the recommended configuration is for an equal weighting between the two, to provide an overall trustworthiness score for a given LLM response.

The metric fusion methodology resulted in a significant improvement in correlation with human judgement across all domains tested; specifically, the correlation for Long-Form Question Answering (QA) increased from a previous best of 0.756 to 0.969, and the correlation for Summarisation increased from 0.636 to 0.761. The Explainable Boosting Machine (EBM) algorithm was selected and utilized to calculate metric weightings for the faithfulness fusion, ensuring that the combined score maximized similarity with human judgment. The fusion process demonstrated that graph-based metrics were consistently deemed highly important for the overall fused metric output across tasks, despite having weak individual correlations; they were found to be important within the more ambiguous and long-form dialogue summarisation domain but less critical for the simpler Short-Form QA task. The readability score was deliberately excluded from the final explainability metric because the desired reading level is highly subjective and dependent upon the individual user, making it unsuitable for a generalized metric. The components of the explainability metric (Confidence and Explanation) are equally weighted because the metric's objective is to provide the rationale behind a decision rather than attempting to simulate or correlate with subjective human judgment, which distinguishes its fusion approach from the faithfulness metric.

8 Conclusion

Deliverable 1.2 has covered extensive literature review, aiming to identify metrics for faithfulness and explainability that can be incorporated into a fused metric. The faithfulness metric methodology was developed using the annotated human judgements from the ELOQUENCE fused dataset and correlating automated metrics against these ground truths for question answering, conversational question answering and dialogue summarisation domains. Various metrics were trialled, including AMR graphs, LLM-as-a-judge, BERTScore, matching and n-grams. All metrics, LLM responses and human judgements have been implemented into the publicly available fused dataset. Similar evaluation has been performed for pilot data, with Pilot 4 comparing the alignment of LLM-as-a-judge techniques to human evaluators in Serbian, finding high alignment between LLM responses and expert human judges. Pilot 1 have produced a Spanish, dialogue-oriented, question answering dataset, which has been evaluated against a range of metrics to determine the faithfulness of the LLM.

In addition to the faithfulness work, explainability research and experimentation has been conducted. The use of AMR graphs to illustrate concepts to the user has been trialed and implemented within the ELOQUENCE fused dataset. Comparably, work has been conducted to model the flow of dialogues using graphs, which can better illustrate discrepancies and desirable dialogue flows. Furthermore, explainability evaluation has been conducted using LLM and RAG-based approaches for the ELOQUENCE fused dataset, so that numerical values can be extrapolated and utilised for an eMetric. This aligns with the literature review conducted on readability evaluation, which can calculate the complexity of text (a facet of explainability). Experimental evaluation of the various readability metrics has been conducted on Pilot 2's data.

However, future milestones and deliverables require the integration of additional metrics across a broader range of categories, such as bias and security. Due to these future requirements, extensive literature review has been conducted on these areas and reported upon within this document. Finally, a fused metric has been defined to incorporate the array of faithfulness metrics and explainability metrics that have been evaluated, so that ongoing progress and developments can be reported on and easily evaluated for improvements.

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